

16th ISAJ Annual Symposium - 2025

CIRCULAR INNOVATION FOR URBAN TRANSFORMATION & BEYOND

Japan-India Symposium on Science & Technology

PROGRAM & ABSTRACTS

November 28 (Fri)-29 (Sat), 2025

Venue: Shizuoka Institute of Science
& Technology (SIST),
Shizuoka Ekimae Campus,
Shizuoka City

Indian Scientists Association in Japan

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<https://isaj.jp>

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Messages

MESSAGE

It is an honour to extend my warm greetings to all distinguished participants, organizers, and guests attending the 16th ISAJ Symposium in Shizuoka, especially those who have contributed presentations, scientific papers and posters. The Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) continues to play a pivotal role in forging new pathways for scientific cooperation and innovation between India and Japan. I am pleased to note that this year's theme, "Circular Innovation for Urban Transformation and Beyond," makes a special focus on the urgent challenges and opportunities of sustainable development.

Over the years, India has witnessed remarkable transformation in its science, technology, and education sectors. This is reflected in India's rising global rankings in research output and innovation. Japan remains a principal and valued partner in this journey of India. This year we celebrate "**India-Japan Year of Science, Technology and Innovation Exchange**", a fitting marker of the bilateral relationship.

I am confident that the ISAJ Symposium will bring together leading researchers, young scholars, and innovators from both countries, and the presentations, discussions, and networking opportunities here will catalyze new collaborations, inspire creative solutions, and contribute meaningfully to sustainable futures.

I convey my best wishes for a successful symposium and for the continued advancement of India-Japan scientific engagement.

(Nagma M. Mallick)
Ambassador of India to Japan

November 24, 2025

On behalf of the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ), we extend a warm and heartfelt welcome to all distinguished delegates and guests attending the 16th ISAJ Annual Japan-India Symposium on Science & Technology, titled *“Circular Innovation for Urban Transformation & Beyond”*, taking place on November 28-29, 2025, in Shizuoka City. We are excited to offer an intellectually stimulating and thought-provoking platform for meaningful exchange.

Founded in 2008, ISAJ is a non-profit organization (NPO) that serves as a vibrant community hub for Indian scientists and researchers based in Japan. In January 2009, Dr. R. Chidambaram, the then Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India, inaugurated ISAJ in the esteemed presence of His Excellency Hemant Krishan Singh, the former Ambassador of India to Japan. Since then, ISAJ has made significant strides in fostering academic collaboration and promoting scientific excellence.

In 2010, ISAJ was officially registered as a non-profit entity in Japan, underscoring its commitment to advancing scientific growth and facilitating cross-cultural research partnerships. Over the years, ISAJ has been at the forefront of organizing seminars, community discussions, and networking opportunities, catering to a broad spectrum of individuals—from undergraduate students to seasoned professionals in academia and industry.

ISAJ has played an instrumental role in strengthening India-Japan scientific ties, offering Indian students invaluable training opportunities in Japan and fostering enhanced scientific exchange between the two nations. Through these efforts, ISAJ has significantly contributed to the mutual growth of both countries' scientific and technological landscapes.

The Annual Symposium has been a flagship event in ISAJ's calendar for the past 15 years, and we are immensely proud to celebrate its 16th edition. This symposium has consistently provided a unique platform for Indian researchers and their Japanese counterparts to showcase cutting-edge research. Each year, we see dynamic, multidisciplinary participation from diverse fields. From its early years, hosted at the Embassy of India in Tokyo, to its expansion to prestigious venues such as Tokyo University, AIST Tsukuba, Osaka University, and Hokkaido University, the symposium has evolved and adapted to changing times. The 12th Symposium in Shimizu, Shizuoka, marked the transition to a hybrid format, combining in-person and virtual presentations. At the same time, the 13th and 14th editions continued this trend with both in-person and digital engagement. This year, we are delighted to host the symposium at the Shizuoka Institute of Science & Technology, and we are particularly excited to celebrate the India-Japan Year of Science, Technology, and Innovation Exchange.

In keeping with tradition, we remain committed to preserving the symposium's interdisciplinary focus, creating a dynamic environment for participants to exchange ideas, share experiences, and build collaborations. The scientific presentations over the years have highlighted the growing and diverse involvement of Indian researchers in Japan across multiple fields, and we are particularly encouraged by the increasing number of Indian researchers rising through the ranks to take on faculty positions in Japan and esteemed universities in India.

We look forward to engaging with all our esteemed guests and to fostering insightful discussions. The presentations by young researchers have always been a highlight of our symposiums, and we are confident that this year will be no exception. We also anticipate valuable insights from senior scientists, whose vast experience and contributions to India-Japan scientific cooperation continue to inspire us all.

This symposium presents a unique opportunity for all participants to step beyond their daily research routines and engage in meaningful exchanges. We are confident that the interactions and collaborations that emerge from this event will offer significant benefits for both young Indian researchers and students.

We want to extend our sincere gratitude to Her Excellency Ms. Nagma Mohamed Mallick, the Ambassador of India to Japan, and Prof. Masakazu Kimura, President of the Shizuoka Institute of Science & Technology, as well as to all the distinguished dignitaries who have joined us for this momentous occasion. We sincerely appreciate all our guests for accepting our invitation and contributing to the success of this event.

We hope that all participants find the symposium both enjoyable and enriching, and that they seize the opportunity to forge new connections, build lasting friendships, and collaborate, thereby further strengthening the enduring bond of scientific and technological cooperation between India and Japan.

With best regards,

(Sunil Kaul)
Chairman

(Alok Singh)
Vice-Chairman

(Kedarnath Mahapatra)
General Secretary

Conveners' Message

On behalf of the Symposium Organizing Committee, we, the conveners, extend our warmest welcome to all our esteemed guests and participants joining us for the 16th Annual Symposium of the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ). This year's theme, "***Circular Innovation for Urban Transformation & Beyond***," reflects our shared aspiration to foster sustainable, inclusive, and forward-looking urban futures. In celebration of 2025–2026 as the India–Japan Year of Science, Technology, and Innovation Exchange, the symposium's first day will spotlight the vital role of the Japan–India partnership/exchange in advancing circular innovation and transformative technologies for India's urban development.

We are deeply grateful to the Shizuoka Institute of Science and Technology (SIST) for being the generous co-organizer and their steadfast support, and to the Embassy of India in Japan for their encouragement and facilitation in bringing this event to life. To all our participants, especially those who have traveled long distances, we sincerely thank you for your time, enthusiasm, and commitment to sharing your research. We are delighted to report that this year's symposium has received an overwhelming number of submissions, culminating in **59 scientific presentations** across two days, including keynote, plenary, invited, and poster sessions. The presentations on the first day will focus on urban transformation themes relevant to both India and Japan, while the second day will feature a rich array of multidisciplinary topics.

We take this opportunity to acknowledge the tireless efforts of the Organizing Committee, with special thanks to Dr. Alok Singh, Vice Chairman of ISAJ, for his invaluable guidance, and to Ms. Helen Sibi and Mr. Raju Samanta for their meticulous coordination and unwavering dedication in making this event possible within a remarkably short timeframe. We are also profoundly thankful to our generous sponsors and donors—The Indian Commerce and Industry Association Japan (ICIJ), Sai Hira India Foundation (SHIF), Suzuyo Construction Co., Ltd., Forecast Ocean Plus, Inc., and Ambika Corporation—whose financial support has been instrumental in the successful organization of this symposium.

We hope that the stimulating deliberations, cross-disciplinary networking during the symposium, and the serene beauty of Shizuoka and Mt. Fuji will inspire and energize your ongoing research endeavors. Please enjoy the presentations, interactions, and the vibrant exchange of ideas over these two days.

Thank you once again, and welcome!

Conveners:

Prof. Kedarnath Mahapatra

Dr. Soumyaranjan Ratha

16th Annual Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)
Circular Innovation for Urban Transformation & Beyond
28-29th November 2025
SIST Ekimae Campus, Shizuoka City

PL: Plenary talk; IL: Invited talk; OR: Oral presentation; P: Poster presentation

Time	November 28 th , 2025 (Friday) (Simultaneous interpretation in English/Japanese)	
12:00-13:00	Registration	
13:00-15:00	Opening Session (MC: Prof. Takahiro Nishida)	
13:00	<p>Welcome Address: Prof. Kedarnath Mahapatra, Convener of Symposium, Shizuoka Institute of Science & Technology</p> <p>Opening Address: Prof. Masakazu Kimura, President, Shizuoka Institute of Science & Technology</p> <p>Dr. Yashawant Dev Panwar, Counsellor (Science & Technology), Embassy of India</p>	
13:20	<p>Keynote: Prof. Muralidhar Miryala, Shibaura Institute of Technology <i>High-Tc Superconductors: Key Technology for Net-Zero Energy Future</i></p>	<i>Abstract Page 2</i>
13:50	<p>Special Plenary: Dr. Kuniaki Minami, Japan Railway Construction, Transport and Technology Agency <i>Technical Exchange Between Japan and India for Quality Assurance of Steel Bridges in the Mumbai–Ahmedabad High-Speed Rail Project</i></p>	3
14:20	<p>Special Plenary: Mr. Yoshiya Nakagawa, PADECO Co. Ltd. <i>Urban Transformation in Mumbai through Underground Railway</i></p>	5
14:50	Concluding Remarks	
15:00	Group Photo & Coffee Break	
15:30-17:00	Plenary Session [Chair: Tomonori Tominaga]	
15:30	<p>Special Invited: Mr. Yuji Nishikawa, JST <i>Promoting Science and Technology Partnerships: JST's International Programs for Young Researchers from India and Other Countries</i></p>	6
15:45 Cancelled	<p>PL-1 Satsuki Goto, Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) <i>JICA's Technical Cooperation in Wastewater and Sludge Management in India: Current Engagement and Future Collaboration</i></p>	7
16:05	<p>PL-2 Remi Chandran, Remote Sensing Technology Center of Japan <i>The Importance of Digital Public Infrastructure for People and Planet: Addressing Human–Nature Conflicts Across Asia and Africa</i></p>	8
16:25	<p>PL-3 Tomoya Inami, Shizuoka Institute of Science and Technology <i>A New Processing Technique for the Sustainable Use of Rice Husks and Residues to Address the Urban Air Pollution Problem in North India</i></p>	9

16:45	PL-4 Shohei Koike , Showa Sekkei, Shizuoka <i>Establishing a Control System for Alligator Weed (<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i>) through Industry-Government-Academia-Civil Society Collaboration - Background and Approaches in the Case of Asahata Retention Basin</i>	10
17:00	Panel Discussion	
17:30	Concluding Remarks	

Time	November 29 th , 2025 (Saturday)	
08:30-09:25	Registration	
09:00-10:00	Opening Session (MC: Dr. Renu Wadhwa)	
09:00	Welcome Address: Dr. Sunil Kaul, Chairman, ISAJ	
	Opening Address: Prof. Masakazu Kimura, President, SIST	
09:10	Inaugural Address: (video message) H.E. Ms. Nagma Mohamed Mallick Ambassador of India to Japan	
09:20	Conveners Address: Prof. Kedarnath Mahapatra, SIST	
09:25	Vote of Thanks , Dr. Alok Singh, Vice-Chairman, ISAJ	
09:30	Group Photo	
9:40-12:00	Session I [Chairs: Renu Wadhwa, Sridhara Nayak]	
9:40	PL-5 Satoru Yoshimura , Akita University <i>Development Spatial Light Modulator for Realization of 3D Display with Low Power Consumption and High Brightness with Using Multiferroic Thin Films and Their Laminated Films</i>	12
10:00	PL-6 Takahiro Nishida , Shizuoka Institute of Science and Technology <i>Selection of Highly Alkaline-Resistant Bacteria for Self-Healing Concrete</i>	13
10:20	PL-7 Akiko Yamamoto , National Institute for Materials Science <i>Development of New In Vitro Evaluation Methods for Biomedical Application of Biodegradable Metals</i>	14
10:40	IL-1 Manako Tanaka , Tokyo University of the Arts <i>Recent Advances in Nondestructive Analytical Methods for Iron Cultural Heritage: Complementary Use of Synchrotron Radiation, Neutrons, and Muons</i>	20
10:55	IL-2 Deepa Kasaragod , Hiroshima University <i>Deep Ultraviolet Light-based Open Microscopy for Imaging Three-Dimensional Structures in the Mouse Brain</i>	21
11:10	IL-3 Shreya Santra , Tohoku University <i>from Mines to Moon: Intelligent Multi-Robot Systems and the Next Leap in Space Exploration</i>	22

11:25	IL-4	Kazumi Hirano , National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) <i>Seaweed-derived Compound Fucoxanthin Protects Cells from Stress Associated with Alzheimer's Disease</i>	23
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13:30	PL-8	Yukiko Takahashi , National Institute for Materials Science <i>Development of Magnetic Materials for Environmentally Friendly Society</i>	15
13:50	PL-9	Sridhara Nayak , Japan Meteorological Corporation <i>Modeling of Extreme Events for Resilient and Sustainable Cities</i>	16
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14:15	IL-5	Tomoyo Ochiishi , National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) <i>A Mouse Model of Mild Cognitive Impairment for Screening Therapeutic Candidates for Alzheimer's Disease</i>	24
14:30	IL-6	Swagatha Ghosh , Nagoya University <i>Deciphering Structural Intermediates of a Red Fluorescent Protein Sandercyanin using Serial Crystallography Techniques</i>	25
14:45	IL-7	Jeevan Kumar Padarti , Kitami Institute of Technology <i>Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) in Battery Research: Slurry Dispersion to Solid-state Interfaces</i>	26
15:00	IL-8	Arghya Dutta , National Institute for Materials Science <i>Lithium-Air Batteries: Turning Air into Energy</i>	27
15:15	OR-2	Biplab Manna , National Institute for Materials Science <i>Decoding Polymer Chain using Nano Porous Material</i>	35
15:25	OR-3	Megha Khamble , Shivaji University <i>Narrative Repair and Circular Healing: Reimagining Urban Futures Through Trauma Memoirs</i>	36
14:15-15:35	Session II B (Parallel) [Chairs: Agamoni Pathak, A R Dilipan]		
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14:30	IL-10	Aoqier Erideng , Shizuoka Institute of Science and Technology <i>Experimental Study on Porosity Estimation of Pervious Concrete Slabs Using Ultrasonic Wave Method</i>	29
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P9	Yuta Hachigo	SIST	<i>Investigations of Sacrificial Anode Materials and Charging Conditions in Electro-deposition Method of Reinforced Concrete</i>	51
P10	Haruki Toya	SIST	<i>Study on the Incorporation Methods of Bacteria and Organic matters in Self-Healing Concrete</i>	52
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ABSTRACTS

Day 1 Symposium

Circular Innovation for Urban Transformation & Beyond

Keynote

High- T_c Superconductors: A Key Technology for the Net Zero Energy Future

Muralidhar Miryala

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The International Energy Agency's Net Zero Emissions (NZE) policy outlines a clear pathway for transforming the global energy sector to achieve net-zero carbon dioxide emissions by 2050. This goal supports the worldwide effort to limit global warming to around 1.5 °C and contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals — particularly the objective of ensuring universal access to modern energy by 2030. Achieving these ambitious targets requires more than just expanding renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and biomass. It also depends on major innovations in energy storage and the efficient transmission of clean electricity. This is where high-temperature superconducting (high- T_c) technologies come into play. These materials — together with superconducting magnets and cables — are opening up transformative possibilities for the future of energy systems. Prototypes have already demonstrated that superconducting magnets can trap extremely high magnetic fields, and that superconducting cables can transmit megawatts of power without resistance. These advancements are crucial to realizing the NZE vision. In this talk, I will present recent progress in the development of high- T_c superconducting materials and discuss their strategic importance in driving the next generation of clean energy technologies.

Special Plenary

Technical Exchange Between Japan and India for Quality Assurance of Steel Bridges in the Mumbai–Ahmedabad High-Speed Rail Project

Kuniaki Minami

Japan Railway Construction, Transport and Technology Agency

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The Mumbai–Ahmedabad High-Speed Rail (MAHSR) is a standard-gauge, dedicated line connecting Mumbai, India's financial capital and most populous city, with Ahmedabad, an important economic and industrial hub. The line comprises 12 stations and has been designed for a maximum operating speed of 350 km/h, with an initial commercial speed of 320 km/h. The total route length of 508 km is planned to be covered in 2 hours and 7 minutes. The corridor passes through several large cities with populations of several million, offering a demographic potential comparable to that of Japan's Tokaido Shinkansen. To minimize land acquisition, most of the route has been planned as an elevated structure. The structural composition consists of 91.6% of alignments on viaducts, 1.9% bridges, 5.2% tunnels, and 1.3% earthworks and other works. Among these, approximately 70,000 tons of steel for railway bridges, primarily truss bridges, have been planned for construction, with around 80% of the factory fabrication completed as of the end of February 2025.

Initially, based on an intergovernmental agreement, the participation of Japanese companies in joint ventures (JV) was required to ensure quality assurance. However, the Government of India requested that Indian companies be allowed to bid independently. In response, technical exchanges were undertaken between Japan and India to make this possible. In 2019, following requests from JICA and the Railway Bureau of Japan's Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism, the Japan Society of Civil Engineers (JSCE) established the Subcommittee for the Evaluation of Feasibility of "Make in India" (MII) for Steel Railway Bridges, chaired by Senior Distinguished Prof. Yozo Fujino of Yokohama National University (at that time). The committee conducted site visits between September and November 2019, inspecting two factories and one bridge erection site in India, as well as two factories in Japan, to identify quality differences and examine countermeasures to overcome them. As a result, nine new projects aimed at quality improvement were commissioned. In March 2021, a fabrication package for steel bridges was awarded, and fabrication of 28 steel truss bridges (49 spans in total) is currently underway for the MAHSR project. To verify whether the intended quality

assurance objectives were being achieved, a Workshop on Quality Control of Steel Structures and factory site inspections was jointly organized by JICA, NHSRCL, ADBI, and JARTS in February 2024. The inspections confirmed significant improvement in welding quality compared with 2019, while also identifying areas for further enhancement. From 2025 onward, quality control of composite box girders has become a key issue. Although most steel railway bridges on the MAHSR line were originally planned as truss bridges, a shift to composite box girders was necessitated in certain sections intersecting with Indian Railways lines to enhance safety. In total, 34 spans (ranging from 35 m to 50 m) of composite girders were adopted. In February 2025, engineers from NHSRCL and Indian contractors visited the Miyaji Engineering Chiba Factory in Japan, where composite box girders for the Hokkaido Shinkansen were being fabricated, and held discussions with Japanese counterparts. Subsequently, mock-up specimens of the same scale as the actual girders were fabricated in India. In March 2025, at the request of the Indian side, Japanese experts conducted site inspections of fabrication and provided recommendations for quality improvement.

As a result of these collaborative efforts, erection work for steel truss bridges has commenced, with several bridges already successfully erected. Fabrication quality has shown remarkable improvement compared with the situation in 2019. However, some gaps with Japanese quality standards remain. Therefore, continuous on-site guidance by IHI engineers stationed in India remains essential. Ongoing technical support will be maintained, and the Japanese side is eagerly anticipating the successful inauguration of the Mumbai–Ahmedabad High-Speed Rail.

Special Plenary

Urban Transformation in Mumbai through Underground Railway

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Mumbai's contemporary urban transformation has evolved through several strategic initiatives since the 2000s, beginning with the World Bank-supported Mumbai Urban Transport Project (MUTP-I, 2002-2011), which catalyzed the modernization of suburban railways. In 2003, *Vision Mumbai*, a landmark report by McKinsey & Company and Bombay First, presented a blueprint for transforming Mumbai into a world-class city. Subsequently, the Comprehensive Transportation Study (CTS) by LEA International (2005-08) introduced a framework for congestion mitigation through coastal highways and metro networks. These initiatives led to the construction of the Bandra–Worli Sea Link (BWSL) in 2009, the Mumbai Trans Harbor Link (MTHL) and the Coastal Road in 2024, followed by the expansion of Mumbai Metro lines 1, 2A, and, recently, the Line 3 (MML3) fully opened in Oct. 2025.

The next milestone in this continuum is the underground conversion of the Western Railway corridor between Churchgate and Mumbai Central-India's first such project for an existing urban railway. Unlike new metro tunnels, this project involves underground construction beneath active railway operations within a narrow right-of-way, demanding precision engineering to control ground settlement to within a few millimeters.

Japan can offer substantial experience in similar challenges, such as the undergrounding of the Tokyu Toyoko Line in Shibuya, the Keio Line in Chofu, and the Odakyu Line at Shimokitazawa. PADECO Co., Ltd. was commissioned by Mumbai Rail Vikas Corporation (MRVC) in October 2025 to conduct a feasibility study for this underground conversion. Beyond technical aspects, the project envisions urban regeneration on the released surface land, improved connectivity across divided districts, land value capture for fiscal gains, and transit-oriented mixed-use development integrated with the adjacent cricket stadium precinct.

This initiative symbolizes a paradigm shift from conventional transport expansion to innovative, transit-oriented urban renewal, showcasing the potential of Japan–India collaboration for sustainable, globally competitive metropolitan transformation. PADECO has served as a General Consultant on several major transport and urban infrastructure projects in India, including the MTHL, MML3, Delhi Metro Phase 4, and the civil works for the Mumbai–Ahmedabad High-Speed Rail, among others.

Special Invited

Promoting Science and Technology Partnerships: JST's International Programs for Young Researchers from India and other countries

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In 2014, the Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST) launched the Sakura Science Exchange Program. This international youth science exchange program invites the world's talented young people to Japan for a short period with a long-term perspective. The goal is to allow them to come into contact with Japan's cutting-edge science and technology and also to promote interaction with young researchers in Japan. This program provides young researchers from Japan and abroad with the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of one another and establish strong, lasting relationships. It is also expected that young Japanese researchers will be able to participate in a wide range of international networks worldwide through this program. Already, over the past decade, more than 40,000 young people from 83 countries and regions worldwide have participated in this program. Networks have been formed between Japanese and foreign universities, research institutions, local governments, private companies, and other relevant parties.

The LOTUS Program invites and supports talented young researchers from India to participate in research exchanges in Japan. The program aims to strengthen Japan-India joint research efforts by fostering collaborations and building networks between research institutions in Japan and India. Faculty members from both countries will jointly supervise the research projects and exchanges. This opportunity is open to young researchers joining ongoing or upcoming joint research projects between Japanese and Indian academic institutions. Additionally, the program will offer career development support to those interested in pursuing a research career in Japan.

Plenary PL-1

JICA's Technical Cooperation in Wastewater and Sludge Management in India: Current Engagement and Future Collaboration

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India is facing increasing challenges in managing wastewater and sewage sludge, as a result of rapid urbanization and population growth. In response, the Environmental Management and Climate Change Group within the Global Environment Department of JICA has been working to support India's efforts through technical cooperation focused on capacity development.

In this presentation, I will introduce my group's involvement in India's wastewater sector, with a focus on the ongoing Sewage Sludge Management Capacity Development Project and plans for future initiatives, such as promoting wastewater reuse.

Plenary PL-2

The Importance of Digital Public Infrastructure for People and Planet: Addressing Human–Nature Conflicts Across Asia and Africa

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Human–nature conflicts are increasingly escalating across both Asia and Africa, creating significant challenges to environmental sustainability and social stability. These conflicts, which include human-wildlife conflict, poaching, land encroachment, and illegal wildlife trade, are severely impacting ecosystems and local communities. In Africa, the illegal wildlife trade is a major concern, with poaching of rhinos for their horns and elephants for their ivory continuing to threaten endangered species. Human-elephant conflict is also a growing issue, as elephants damage crops or even endanger human lives when they move into agricultural areas in search of food and water. In Asia, particularly Japan, human-wildlife conflict is manifesting through increasing encounters between humans and bears. The rise in bear sightings is largely attributed to changes in climate patterns, which are altering the animals' natural behaviour and pushing them closer to urban areas. These conflicts not only disrupt biodiversity and conservation efforts but also pose significant social and economic challenges for local populations, impacting both national and international policy frameworks. The solution to these pressing issues requires coordinated, cross-border responses, driven by reliable data and underpinned by effective digital governance. The concept of Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) is emerging as a transformative approach to addressing these conflicts. DPI offers a platform for integrating and analysing data from multiple sources—such as satellite imagery, GIS, and remote sensing—enabling timely and actionable insights for wildlife protection, conflict prevention, and conservation management. This plenary talk will introduce DPI as a key tool for enhancing early warning systems and improving cross-border collaboration between countries facing similar challenges. It will highlight how DPI can empower governments, NGOs, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions that mitigate the risks associated with human-wildlife conflicts, such as the illegal wildlife trade and human-elephant or human-bear interactions. Furthermore, the talk will explore the technical, institutional, and policy frameworks necessary for DPI implementation across Asia and Africa. By leveraging international collaboration, particularly between technology institutions in Japan and India, the talk will also highlight the importance of developing a shared infrastructure roadmap for Africa. The session will conclude by identifying next steps for collaboration, securing funding, and building a collective, sustainable future for both regions.

Plenary PL-3

A new processing technique for the sustainable use of rice husks and residues to address the urban air pollution problem in North India

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This study aimed to develop a new processing technology to convert rice husks and residues generated after rice harvest into non-carbonized substances for sustainable use as fertilizer. The results derived from our study so far are as follows: 1) equipment was devised, and the processing method was successfully tested with the rice husks as input 2) After processing the rice husks for two minutes, when the processed and unprocessed rice husks were immersed in distilled water separately, the processed rice husks settled in contrast to the unprocessed samples, confirming the improvement of hydrophilicity. As a result, the processed rice husks can decompose faster by making it easier for microorganisms and extracellular enzymes to break them down when spread on the soil and used as fertilizer. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), saccharification, and other analytical and evaluation techniques are presently being undertaken, which would provide a more detailed indication of the processing technique's effectiveness. We will also consider scaling up the process so that our equipment can handle large amounts of rice husks and residues, including stubbles, which could potentially serve as a sustainable countermeasure to address North India's air pollution problem of stubble/husk burning.

Plenary PL-4

Establishing a Control System for alligator weed (*Alternanthera philoxeroides*) through Industry-Government-Academia-Civil society Collaboration - Background and Approaches in the Case of Asahata Retention Basin in Shizuoka City

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Alligator weed (*Alternanthera philoxeroides*) is a South American aquatic plant with extreme reproductive, regenerative, dispersal, and environmental adaptability. Its characteristics include ease of accidental spread from well-intentioned removal efforts, extreme difficulty of eradication once established, and wide-ranging detrimental impacts on natural ecosystems, flood control, and agriculture, which have led the Japanese government to designate it as an Invasive Alien Species requiring urgent control. Effective methods for mapping its distribution and controlling its spread have not yet been established. So, the current situation necessitates early detection and removal by local volunteers, careful verification by specialists, and coordinated action among diverse stakeholders.

The Asahata Yusuichi (Asahata Retention Basin) is a multi-purpose detention facility located on the upper reaches of the Tomoe River, which runs through urban areas of Shizuoka City, providing functions such as ensuring flood control safety, conserving and utilizing the natural environment, preserving traditional culture, and promoting physical and mental health recovery. However, since 2018, the site has suffered invasion and proliferation of alligator weed, threatening these functions. Therefore, a coordinated control program has been established through collaboration among industry, government, academia, and civil society to implement control measures. This case study presents the context for that multi-stakeholder cooperation, the practical measures adopted, and the lessons learned.

Day 2 Symposium Abstracts

Planery Talks

Plenary PL-5

Development spatial light modulator for realization of 3D display with low power consumption and high brightness with using multiferroic thin films and their laminated films

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Magnetization reversal method using an electric field is a future technology for high performance magnetic devices with lower power consumption. Ferromagnetic and ferroelectricity (multiferroic) materials with magneto-electric effect have been receiving greater attention for this method. The doped BiFeO₃ were reported as multiferroic material with clear ferromagnetic and dielectric hysteresis in room temperature. Although the excellent magnetic properties such as high saturation magnetization, perpendicular magnetic anisotropy, and high Curie temperature are needed to realize the high performance magnetic devices, the magnetic properties of previous BiFeO₃-based thin films are not sufficient for application to the magnetic devices. To realize excellent magnetic properties, pulsed DC reactive sputtering method and various substitution elements were investigated in this study. As the results, the new multiferroic thin films with high saturation magnetization, perpendicular magnetic anisotropy, high Curie temperature, and function of magnetization reversal by applying electric field were obtained. And also, the metallic magnetic thin films with perpendicular magnetic anisotropy, low coercivity, and large magneto optical Kerr effect (MOKE) were obtained. By using these thin films, we are proposing new "MOKE amplification by magnetization transfer with electric field application" type spatial light modulator (SLM) for 3D display with low power consumption and high brightness shown in figure1, and also we are demonstrating the device operation.

Fig.1 Newly proposed SLM for realization of 3D display with low power consumption and high brightness with using "MOKE amplification by magnetization transfer with electric field application".

Plenary PL-6

Selection of Highly Alkaline-Resistant Bacteria for Self-Healing Concrete

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This study aimed to isolate and characterize bacteria capable of metabolic activity under highly alkaline conditions, with potential applications in the development of self-healing concrete materials. To select alkaline-tolerant strains, enrichment cultures were performed using media adjusted to pH 11.6. Two highly alkaline-resistant strains, designated AH1 and AH2, were successfully isolated. Genome analysis indicated that both strains are closely related to *Bacillus altitudinis* and possess genes associated with sporulation and alkaline tolerance. Growth experiments revealed that AH1 can proliferate up to pH 11.5, while AH2 remains viable up to pH 12. Optimization of medium components showed that both strains grow robustly using yeast extract as the sole nutrient source. Furthermore, both strains demonstrated the ability to grow using only PHBV, a biodegradable plastic, as a carbon source. These findings suggest that AH1 and AH2 possess characteristics favorable for incorporation into self-healing concrete systems.

Plenary PL-7

Development of New In Vitro Evaluation Methods for Biomedical Application of Biodegradable Metals

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Biomedical application of magnesium (Mg) alloys as biodegradable metal implants is widely investigated since they are easily corroded by reacting with water in the body fluid. One of the key issues for the success of biodegradable metal implants is to control their degradation properties in the tissue. Clinical cases of Mg alloy bone fixtures reported gas cavity formation in the surrounding tissue; some of them resulted in the delay of fracture healing. Their clinical success depends on the implantation site; reasonable success in chevron osteotomies for hallux valgus, but 40% failure in scaphoid fracture fixation [1]. This suggests that the corrosion of Mg alloy is sensitive for the difference in microenvironment at the implantation site, revealing the difficulty to control their degradation properties to satisfy clinical requirement.

Degradation behavior of Mg alloy implants is often investigated by *in vivo* animal tests, which still have limitations such as difference in species, no replication of pathological conditions, and 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) principles. Appropriate *in vitro* evaluation methods are necessary to accelerate the biomedical application of biodegradable metals. Therefore, we develop a model tissue system to simulate the diffusion rate of ions and gasses through the tissue [2]. This system revealed the effect of diffusion rate on Mg alloy corrosion [3, 4] and gas cavity formation [5]. We also utilize the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy to sequentially observe the corrosion behavior of Mg alloys while culturing mammalian/human cells on the specimen surface [6, 7]. These *in vitro* evaluation methods can contribute to the deeper understanding of the biocorrosion behavior of biodegradable metals and their interaction to different physiological environment including various types of cells.

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Plenary PL-8

Development of Magnetic Materials for Environmentally Friendly Society

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To address global warming, countries around the world are taking various measures, such as limiting greenhouse gas emissions. There are two major approaches to reducing greenhouse gases in the research area of the magnetic materials: the electrification of devices and increasing the data-storage density. In this talk, I will introduce our recent research on permanent magnets and magnetic recording media.

In efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, the electrification of a wide range of devices is progressing rapidly. In such electric devices, motors generate mechanical power, and strong permanent magnets are required for their operation. Currently, the strongest commercial permanent magnet is the neodymium (Nd–Fe–B) magnet; however, it faces several challenges. For example, the operating temperature of traction motors in electric vehicles reaches around 150 °C. Due to its relatively low Curie temperature, a neodymium magnet cannot maintain sufficient performance at such high temperatures. In addition, rare-earth elements involve substantial geopolitical risks, and therefore, the development of magnets that exhibit high performance at elevated temperatures while reducing or avoiding rare-earth usage is strongly desired. Based on this background, we focus on samarium-based magnets and are developing Sm-Fe magnets with the ThMn₁₂-type SmFe₁₂ and the TbCu₇-type SmFe₉. [1]

The second topic concerns storage devices. We are working on increasing the areal density of hard disk drives (HDDs), which serve as the main storage in data centers. HDDs integrate various nanotechnologies—magnetic recording media, read/write heads, servo control, tribology, and more—and advances in each of these technologies contribute to increased storage density. Our research focuses on the high-density magnetic recording media itself, and we are developing next-generation media for high-density HDDs. We have been developing FePt-based magnetic recording media for heat assisted magnetic recording (HAMR) [2]. In this talk, I will discuss the materials science of FePt media and the future prospective for magnetic recording.

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Plenary PL-9

Modeling of Extreme Events for Resilient and Sustainable Cities

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Extreme weather events such as floods, heat waves, droughts, and tropical cyclones are increasing in both frequency and intensity. This trend is creating significant challenges for urban systems and sustainable development. Thus understanding the underlying mechanisms of these events and improving their predictability through systematic observations and modeling is essential for building resilient cities. In this presentation, we will highlight advances in numerical modeling and high-resolution forecasting using cutting-edge technologies such as Doppler Lidar. We will describe how these approaches allow forecasts at resolutions of a few hundred meters and provide actionable information for urban planning and early warning systems. We will also discuss the relevance of these approaches in the context of Japan–India collaboration, where shared research, technology exchange, and capacity building can strengthen urban disaster preparedness and climate adaptation strategies.

Plenary PL-10

Ultra-low-power electronics: controlling electron one by one in silicon nanoscale devices

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Silicon nanodevices form the building blocks of present-day nanoelectronics, either as metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) or as *pn* junction diodes. As device miniaturization advances, the impurities (dopants) present in the nanostructured-channels become discrete, giving rise to atomistic effects, and the Coulomb effect becomes significant, allowing transport based on single-electron tunneling. In our group, we investigate such phenomena in silicon-on-insulator (SOI) thin-film devices fabricated in our lab with Cleanroom facilities.

In nanoscale SOI transistors, when doping is low, individual dopants work as QDs for single-electron tunnelling (SET) [1-8]. When doping concentration is increased, clusters of P-dopants can act as QDs and they may have higher barriers under certain conditions [9,10], allowing SET operation even at room temperature, by combining very high doping concentrations with very low dimensionality [11,12]. In codoped FETs, SET functionalities emerge with higher yield [13], especially at low temperatures, allowing single-photon detectors in a range of wavelengths [14].

In nanoscale diodes, on the other hand, when doped at low concentrations, the individuality of the dopants plays a critical role and can be detected in the low-temperature electrical characteristics [15,16]. More recently, we aim for high concentrations of both P-dopants and B-acceptors so that tunnel (Esaki) diodes can be formed [17]. Under such conditions, band-to-band tunnelling (BTBT) emerges as a key mechanism for transport, with applications possibly extended to tunnel FETs [18]. We reported BTBT mediated by dopant states [19], as well as dopant-induced QDs [20] in the nanoscale depletion layer of our SOI *pn* diodes, so control of electrons one by one demonstrating capabilities for ultra-low-power electronics applications.

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Plenary PL-11

Novel Magnetic Properties of Triangular Spin-1 and Spin-1/2 Antiferromagnets

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Recent studies on the strongly correlated properties of the Columbite family of compounds have intensified due to their novel magnetic and electronic behaviors. These systems offer promising platforms for exploring quantum magnetism and testing predictions from exactly solvable theoretical models [1,2]. Columbites are complex transition metal oxides with the general formula AB_2O_6 , where A- and B-site cations typically exhibit divalent and pentavalent oxidation states, respectively. They crystallize in an orthorhombic structure with space group $Pbcn$ ($D \frac{14}{2h}$). These materials are notable for exhibiting a range of exotic phenomena, including quantum critical behavior, magnetoelectric coupling, tricritical points (Fig. 1), and field-induced metamagnetic transitions [3]. Although naturally occurring magnetic systems are typically three-dimensional, Columbites can often be approximated as quasi-one-dimensional or quasi-two-dimensional systems, depending on the direction of spin-chain coupling. This reduced dimensionality facilitates the observation of quantum phenomena, such as quantum phase transitions near a quantum critical point (QCP) under a transverse magnetic field, enabling experimental realization of the transverse-field Ising chain (TFIC) model. In this work, we highlight these distinctive features and discuss the nature of exchange interactions in selected spin- $1/2$ and spin-1 Columbite compounds [2].

Fig.1: Magnetic field and temperature (H - T) phase diagram of $NiNb_2O_6$ sample for H parallel to the a axis in (a) and H parallel to the c axis yielding a triple point, $TTP (H,T) = (5 \text{ kOe}, 5.50 \text{ K})$ in (b). Lines connecting the data points are visual guides, and references to sources of the data points are listed in the figure. The acronyms used for the magnetic phases are as follows: PM, paramagnetic; AFM, antiferromagnetic; and IFM, induced ferromagnetic.

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Invited Talks

IL-1

Recent Advances in Nondestructive Analytical Methods for Iron Cultural Heritage: Complementary Use of Synchrotron Radiation, Neutrons, and Muons

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Traditionally, the study of materials and manufacturing techniques used in iron cultural heritage objects required cutting the artifacts to observe their metallographic structures. In recent years, however, the application of quantum beam technologies such as synchrotron radiation, neutrons, and muons to cultural heritage research has advanced, enabling the nondestructive acquisition of various types of information. We have been carrying out nondestructive studies on iron cultural heritage objects, including Japanese swords, using synchrotron radiation (high-energy X-ray CT) and neutrons (pulsed neutron transmission spectroscopy). The complementary use of these techniques has enabled us to obtain detailed internal and metallographic information such as crystal structure, crystallite size, density, and strain without causing any damage to the artifacts. More recently, we have initiated a new line of research employing muons. Taking advantage of the fact that the lifetime of negative muons in materials varies depending on the element, we are collaborating with muon specialists to develop a nondestructive analytical method capable of quantifying carbon at ppm levels in iron¹⁾. As an applied study, we are attempting to determine carbon concentrations in Japanese swords. Traditionally, the quantification of trace carbon in steel has required either metallographic observation of cross-sections or combustion analysis, which measures the carbon dioxide generated by burning. In contrast, the negative muon lifetime measurement (MLM) technique provides a nondestructive alternative that requires no sample preparation. This presentation will report the recent advances in nondestructive studies employing synchrotron radiation, neutrons, and muons, with a focus on Japanese swords.

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IL-2

Deep ultraviolet light based open microscopy for imaging three-dimensional structures in the mouse brain

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Deep ultraviolet (DUV) light-emitting diodes (LEDs) have emerged as compact, energy-efficient illumination sources enabling novel optical sectioning techniques in biological imaging. Here, we present the design and implementation of a 280 nm DUV LED-based fluorescence microscope optimized for analysis of 3-dimensional brain structures.

The system utilizes surface-limited excitation in the DUV range to achieve optical sectioning without the need for complex optics or computational deconvolution. Integrating a vibrating microtome with DUV illumination allowed automated 3D imaging of large tissue volumes. Open-source hardware and software solutions, including Arduino-based stage translation controls and μ Manager interfaces, were implemented for flexible, low-cost instrument automation. This study highlights the potential of DUV microscopy as a powerful, yet affordable tool for exploring brain structures at cellular resolution.

IL-3

From Mines to Moon: Intelligent Multi-Robot Systems and the Next Leap in Space Exploration”

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Recent technological progress is transforming the scope of human and robotic exploration, enabling sustained missions to the low-Earth orbit, Moon, Mars, and other deep-space targets. In these distant and extreme environments, robotic systems play a crucial role throughout the mission lifecycle - ranging from early reconnaissance and mapping to autonomous infrastructure deployment and long-duration operations. Their ability to function in environments that are physically inaccessible or hazardous for humans makes them essential for advancing science, enabling infrastructure, and reducing mission risk. Advances in AI are opening new frontiers for adaptive policy learning and bridging the persistent gap between simulation and real-world performance. Intelligent multi-agent cooperative systems have the potential to significantly enhance the adaptability and autonomy of modular robotic platforms used for in-situ construction and infrastructure development. My current work focuses on the development of modular, reconfigurable robots that leverage Decentralized Reinforcement Learning (Dec-RL) and Generative AI to acquire generalizable skills, coordinate as teams, plan tasks dynamically, and adapt to unfamiliar environments without explicit reprogramming. This framework reduces reliance on predefined routines, enabling self-organizing behaviors and resilient operation under changing mission conditions. Such autonomy also strengthens human-robot collaboration, promoting efficient construction and maintenance of lunar facilities with minimal human intervention. In addition, I will share insights from my research journey from a small mining town in India and perspectives on emerging trends in space exploration, emphasizing the expanding role of robotics and AI in shaping humanity’s next steps in and beyond Earth.

Seaweed-derived compound fucoxanthin protects cells from stress associated with Alzheimer's disease

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INTRODUCTION. Fucoxanthin is a carotenoid found in marine seaweeds and is known for its potent antioxidant properties. Oxidative stress is a key contributor to many age-related diseases, including metabolic syndrome and neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease, which are characterized by molecular damage and abnormal protein aggregation. The use of natural compounds for managing cellular stress is expected to reduce disease burden and improve overall health outcomes. In this context, we screened natural compounds for their ability to reverse protein aggregation and identified fucoxanthin as a promising candidate.

METHODS. An *in vitro* screening system based on amyloid β ($A\beta$) aggregation—an established hallmark of Alzheimer's disease—was developed to identify compounds with protein de-aggregation potential. Cultured cell and cerebral organoid models were then used to examine the effects of fucoxanthin under various stress conditions, including heat shock, tunicamycin-induced endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, sodium arsenite ($NaAsO_2$, heavy metal stress), and cellular senescence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Fucoxanthin was identified as a compound with significant protein de-aggregation activity. Treatment with tunicamycin induced ER stress, and subsequent analysis revealed that fucoxanthin protected cultured cells from oxidative and DNA damage-related stress. Notably, it markedly reduced protein aggregation, as demonstrated by GFP/luciferase aggregation assays. In brain-derived cultured cells and cerebral organoids exposed to tunicamycin, fucoxanthin treatment attenuated cellular stress responses. Furthermore, fucoxanthin reduced expression of the senescence marker p16 and levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in senescent human fibroblasts. These findings suggest an anti-aging potential of fucoxanthin, likely mediated through its broad protective effects against multiple forms of cellular stress.

CONCLUSION. In summary, fucoxanthin—an abundant bioactive molecule derived from wakame seaweed—acts as a multi-functional anti-stress compound and may help maintain cellular homeostasis and quality of life under both endogenous and environmental stress conditions

IL-5

A Mouse Model of Mild Cognitive Impairment for Screening Therapeutic Candidates for Alzheimer's Disease

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In Alzheimer's disease (AD), memory impairment occurs prior to the formation of amyloid plaques and neuronal loss. Recent studies suggest that this impairment may be caused by intracellular amyloid- β (A β) oligomers. We have developed a transgenic mouse model (A β -GFP Tg mouse) that expresses a fusion protein of A β and GFP, which forms only low-molecular-weight A β oligomers exclusively within neurons. This model does not exhibit amyloid plaque formation, neurofibrillary tangles, or brain atrophy, but shows cognitive impairment, reduced long-term potentiation, altered spine morphology, and oxidative stress from 2-3months of age. Therefore, it is a model mouse specifically designed for analyzing the toxicity of A β oligomers in the early stages of AD. Recently, the effects of many natural agents have been tested to reduce the neurotoxicity of A β . Anthocyanins are polyphenolic flavonoids with antioxidant and neuroprotective properties, and are potential therapeutic candidates for AD. Here, we investigated the effects of anthocyanin-enriched extracts from fruits of mulberry (*Morus alba* Linn.; ME) in Thailand against the neurotoxicity of A β oligomers. Using the monitoring system for A β aggregation that we developed, we revealed that the extract induced the dissociation of A β oligomers in cultured HEK293T cells. The ME was orally administrated once a day to the A β -GFP Tg mice for totally 40 days and the behavioral experiments were started at 3 weeks after the first day of administration. The open-field test showed no differences in general motor activity and exploratory behavior among vehicle-treated non-Tg, vehicle-treated A β -GFP Tg, and ME-treated A β -GFP Tg mice. Both in the novel object recognition test and passive avoidance test, memory impairment in A β -GFP Tg mice improved significantly compared with vehicle-treated A β -GFP Tg mice after ME treatment. A β -GFP Tg mice exhibited lower superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity than non-Tg mice. However, after the ME treatment, the SOD activity was recovered. These results suggest that the ME may be an effective therapeutic or preventive candidate for early stage of AD.

IL-6

Deciphering structural intermediates of a red fluorescent protein Sandercyanin using serial crystallography techniques

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Red fluorescent proteins (RFPs) have innumerable applications in cell biology and specially advantageous for deep-tissue imaging due to their fluorescence in the red to near- infrared spectrum [1]. Sandercyanin, a biliverdin (BV)- bound red fluorescent protein found in the skin mucus of walleye fish (*Stizostedion vitreum*), is known for its UV protection properties in the fish [2,3]. We have characterized Sandercyanin using crystal structures and UV-visible spectroscopy. Our studies reveal a small protein with bright and photostable far- red fluorescence and an exceptionally large spectral shift of ~300 nm [3]. On binding non-covalently to BV, the chromophore is stabilized by aromatic- stacking, and water-mediated hydrogen bonding interactions within the core of the protein giving rise to its unique spectral properties [3-5]. In our current research, using serial X-ray crystallography (SX) techniques [6], we aim to elucidate the molecular basis of spectral heterogeneity of BV-Sandercyanin FP complex. Previously, structures obtained by single crystals diffraction were insufficient to elucidate the transient states of modulated spectral properties [4,5], hence we applied advanced SX to our study. We have achieved optimal microcrystallization and obtained SX- structures of wild-type Sandercyanin and a weak- fluorescing variant. These structures demonstrate the structural intermediates associated with the altered fluorescence. The goal of our project is to decipher the structural mechanisms associated with fluorescence energy transfer using time-resolved SX techniques [6] and bioengineer Sandercyanin to stabilize BV- binding for in vivo applications. Till date, Sandercyanin remains the first vertebral-based red FP and uniquely known in the lipocalin protein family [3]. We believe that a well- characterized bright and stable Sandercyanin could be tailored to a variety of novel applications in life science research.

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Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in battery research: Slurry dispersion to solid-state interfaces

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Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) has become an essential tool for understanding and optimizing lithium-ion and all-solid-state batteries. Its ability to separate charge-transfer reactions, ionic transport, double-layer behavior, and diffusion processes across frequency ranges makes it uniquely powerful for linking fundamental electrochemistry with practical performance. In this talk, I will highlight how frequency-resolved impedance signatures reveal dispersion states in conductive-carbon slurries, capturing the transition from isolated carbon black domains to continuous percolation networks. I will also discuss how similar principles extend to solid-state systems, where nanoscale Ta-doped $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZTO) coatings on Li-ion battery cathode and precursor chemistry control interfacial stability, charge-transfer resistance, and long-term cycling [1,2]. By connecting particle-level interactions with electrode architecture and interface engineering, this presentation outlines a unified EIS-based approach for guiding materials selection, processing strategies, and durability design in next-generation high-energy batteries.

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Lithium–Air Batteries: Turning Air into Energy

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Lithium-Air (Li-Air) batteries are among the most promising next-generation energy storage technologies, offering a theoretical energy density nearly ten times higher than that of conventional lithium-ion batteries. Their operation is based on the reversible reaction between lithium ions and oxygen from air, forming lithium peroxide (Li_2O_2) during discharge. Li-Air systems hold great potential as lightweight, high-capacity, transition-metal-free, and sustainable power sources for electric vehicles and large-scale energy storage. However, their practical application remains limited by low energy efficiency, poor reversibility, slow rate, and short cycle life.

The low energy efficiency and poor reversibility primarily arise from the difficulty in decomposing the highly insulating Li_2O_2 during recharge. In addition, restricted oxygen diffusion and poor electrode stability, both closely linked to the design of the carbon-based air electrode, lower the rate-capability and cycle life of the battery. The porous carbon electrode provides the framework for oxygen diffusion and its reduction and evolution reactions, while also governing the nucleation, growth, and decomposition of Li_2O_2 . Inadequate control over these processes leads to pore clogging, parasitic side reactions between carbon and reactive oxygen species, and irreversible structural degradation, all of which severely limit cycling stability.

This presentation will focus on strategies for designing optimized carbon electrodes to address these challenges. Key approaches include tailoring pore structures to regulate Li_2O_2 deposition, enhancing oxygen transport, and improving capacity/energy density. A well-engineered carbon electrode can thus serve as the foundation for transforming oxygen from air into clean, sustainable, and high-density electrical energy.

IL-9

Low Power Long-Range Hybrid Time-of-Flight CMOS Image Sensor for Outdoor Operations

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Various types of time-of-flight (ToF) imagers, employing either direct ToF (dToF) or indirect ToF (iToF), have recently been developed to perform effectively in outdoor environments with strong ambient light. The dToF imagers are well placed for long range applications while they still have difficulty having high depth-image resolution. On the other hand, iToF imagers using short pulse (SP) are more effective for outdoor operation under strong background light due to the reduced in-pixel ambient light charge acquisition shot noise, while having a high range-image resolution [1, 2]. For extended range measurements, flash-type light sources require higher optical power, resulting in increased power consumption. In contrast, scanning light sources offer an effective solution for reducing the required optical power to achieve specified precision, particularly in strong ambient light conditions, or for enhancing precision under limited optical power. This approach focuses the light on a small region of the target scene for a shorter duration, minimizing the amount of ambient light charge collected.

In this study, we developed a novel multi-zone light-tracing hybrid Time of Flight (LT-hToF) imaging technique that combines both advantages of scanning light sources and hybrid ToF measurements where the ToF of a short pulse is measured by both direct and indirect ways. To do this, the designed hToF sensor has a function of activation and inactivation control of a set of pixel columns. The proposed technique is very suitable for outdoor extended range measurement under strong ambient light conditions with reduced light-source power.

The light power of the 12-zone scanning VCSEL light source used for the measurements is 200mW (average) and 4W(peak). Theoretically, achieving the same range measurement performance using flash illumination requires 12 times more power in scenes where ambient light shot noise is the dominant noise component.

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IL-10

Experimental Study on Porosity Estimation of Pervious Concrete Slabs Using Ultrasonic Wave Method

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This study experimentally investigates the effectiveness of using the ultrasonic wave velocity test (surface method) to estimate the porosity of vibration-compacted pervious concrete slabs. The slabs were fabricated under various vibration compaction conditions, and the ultrasonic wave velocities were measured to estimate porosity.

A relationship between porosity and ultrasonic wave velocity was established using mold specimens made with the same concrete mix, where ultrasonic measurements were conducted using the direct transmission method. The applicability of this relationship to porosity prediction in actual slabs was examined. Furthermore, a comparison was made with a similar relationship derived from core specimens extracted from the slabs.

As a result, both mold and core specimens showed that the relationships between porosity and ultrasonic wave velocity could be approximated using quadratic functions with similar coefficients. However, the use of the equation based on mold specimens provided more accurate porosity estimation. These results suggest that the ultrasonic surface wave method, when combined with calibration data from mold specimens, is a practical and reliable technique for non-destructive porosity assessment and quality control of field-placed pervious concrete slabs. This approach could contribute to the development of efficient on-site evaluation methods for permeable concrete, which is increasingly used for sustainable infrastructure applications.

IL-11

Micro-lasers: Fluorescent Materials and Art of Light Confinement

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Since their invention in 1960, lasers have become indispensable across many fields — from basic science to manufacturing, communications, healthcare, and defence. Now, micro-/nano-lasers are opening up new possibilities in laser displays, integrated photonics, optical computing, and bio-imaging. Their performance fundamentally relies on optical gain materials and resonator architectures that amplify light within a microcavity (whispering-gallery or Fabry-Pérot cavity). Therefore, exploring novel gain materials and innovative methods is critical to unleash the next-generation technological revolutions of laser science.

Organic/Inorganic fluorescent gain materials offer unique applications owing to structural flexibility, color tunability, and functionality, when embedded within high quality factor (Q) micro-resonators (spheres, disks, droplets). The strong confinement enables low-threshold lasing and spectral tunability via changes in cavity geometry, refractive index environment, or gain medium composition. Furthermore, the use of functional fluorescent materials allows colour tuning and responsiveness to external stimuli (chemical, mechanical, optical) that are useful for sensing, flexible photonics, quantum optics, and bio-imaging.

This talk will cover the following: (1) the rational design of fluorescent gain materials for micro-laser applications; (2) micro-resonator fabrication and light-confinement strategies; (3) the coupling of fluorophore gain media and microcavity feedback to achieve lasing action and tunable emission; and (4) demonstration of key performance metrics (thresholds, linewidths, tunability). In conclusion, by combining materials chemistry, optical physics, and device engineering in one cohesive framework, we explore the fundamental advances in materials science and device physics that underpin the development of next-generation micro-lasers.

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IL-12

Smart Fluorescent Nanomaterials for Biomedical Applications

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Quantum dots (QDs) are nanoscale materials known for their exceptional optical and electronic properties, including tunable fluorescence, high quantum yields, and strong resistance to photobleaching. These features make them ideal candidates for multiplexed imaging and targeted drug delivery detection. Among various types, silicon and carbon-based quantum dots have emerged as especially promising for biological applications due to their high biocompatibility and safety profiles. Silicon quantum dots benefit from the material's widespread use in electronics and its natural compatibility with biological systems. Meanwhile, carbon-based quantum dots offer advantages such as excellent water solubility, low toxicity, environmental friendliness, and cost-effective synthesis, all while exhibiting desirable optical characteristics. In this presentation, both silicon and carbon quantum dots were employed for bioimaging in cells and medaka fish, as well as for tracking DNA-based drug delivery (Figure.1). The results demonstrate the potential of these quantum dots as effective and versatile fluorescent probes for a range of biomedical applications.

Figure 1. The schematic diagram illustrates the process of producing silicon quantum dots from the triethoxysilane precursor, which involves hydrosilylation with 1-decene and functionalization with Pluronic-F127. The resulting SiQD-De/F127 micelle is used as a safe and biocompatible staining agent in both in vitro and in vivo models. Additionally, a two-dimensional image demonstrates the interaction of IgG with the surface of the SiQD-De/F127 micelle.

For abstract IL-13 → see P17 (page 59)

IL-14

From Nanocrystal Morphology to PEC Sensors: Engineering High-Performance Detection Platforms

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The frequent emergence of viral and pathogen outbreaks necessitates the development of rapid and reliable diagnostic tools. Conventional techniques, such as RT-PCR and immunochromatography, each have their drawbacks—RT-PCR, though highly sensitive, is labor-intensive and time-consuming, while immunochromatography provides quicker results but lacks accuracy. To overcome these limitations, we are developing an advanced self-powered photoelectrochemical (PEC) biosensor capable of ultra-sensitive virus detection. PEC biosensors leverage light-driven chemical reactions to produce an electrical signal, enabling highly precise detection of trace viral particles. A major focus of our study is the controlled synthesis of metal-functionalized semiconductor nanorods, a challenging area due to difficulties in structural regulation. We have successfully devised a method for selectively depositing copper (Cu) nanoparticles on one end of CdSe@CdS nanorods, forming a distinctive nanostructure. Cu with interesting plasmonic properties by precisely modulating reaction conditions, we ensured controlled deposition while preventing undesired cation exchange. The structural diversity of these advanced nanoscale materials serves as a basis for the shape–activity correlation studies. These engineered nanostructures enable virus detection at concentrations as low as 3.5 fg/mL. This platform offers exceptional sensitivity, specificity, and stability, making it a powerful tool for early disease diagnosis. Additionally, our synthesis approach paves the way for developing multifunctional nanomaterials for broader applications in healthcare and biosensing.

Oral Presentations

OR-1

Electrochemical Fabrication of Reduced Graphene Oxide Hybrid Thin Films Using Bifunctional Metal Salt Electrolytes

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The electrochemical reduction of graphene oxide (GO) has emerged as a promising, facile, and single-step technique for fabricating electrically conductive films directly on demand substrates. In this study, the electrochemical system was extended to encompass electrolytes containing transition and rare-earth metal ions, which exhibit a bifunctional character by concurrently reducing GO and facilitating the in situ deposition of metal hydroxide or oxide nanocrystals. The efficacy of this strategy in fabricating reduced graphene oxide (rGO)-based functional hybrid thin films is exemplified by a representative case employing a $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ electrolyte. Under these conditions, CeO_2 nanocrystals were uniformly anchored onto the rGO layers. The resulting CeO_2 -rGO hybrid thin films demonstrated superior electrical conductivity compared with those synthesized using conventional or alternative metal-based electrolytes, attributed to enhanced crystallinity of the rGO framework and potential electron-doping effects. Upon optimization of the processing parameters, the hybrid films achieved a sheet resistance as low as $500 \Omega/\square$ while maintaining an optical transparency of 75%, representing one of the highest performance metrics reported to date for rGO-based transparent conductive films. This electrochemical approach therefore offers a versatile platform for the scalable fabrication of rGO-based functional hybrid materials with prospective industrial relevance.

Figure caption: Schematic representation of electrochemical fabrication of rGO-nanocrystal composite on insulating substrate

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OR-2

Decoding polymer chain using nano porous Material

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Microstructures of polymer chains play a critical role in determining their properties. Therefore, researchers have devoted considerable efforts to developing techniques for synthesizing polymers with a controlled microstructure. However, there has been limited exploration into methods for identifying such microstructures of synthetic polymers. This study reports a new strategy for recognizing the monomer structures, compositions, and sequences of synthetic co polymers by introducing them into nano-sized pores of a metal organic framework (MOF)^[1] (Fig. 1).

Fig.1: Schematic illustration of polymer Chain decoding using MOF material

This technology is expected to create a new trend in separating and characterizing synthetic co polymers. Notably, this paradigm redefines the role of synthetic polymers from to serving as new information media, like how biosystems use nucleotide sequences of DNA as genetic information storage.^[2]

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OR-3

Narrative Repair and Circular Healing: Reimagining Urban Futures Through Trauma Memoirs

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Circular innovation is often conceived in terms of technology, materials and economies but we often overlook emotional, cultural infrastructures and narrative systems. Rapidly moving towards advancements without solving the existing issues in society feels like a dissatisfactory achievement. In reimagining sustainable urban transformation, innovation must expand beyond infrastructure and technology to include emotional, cultural, and narrative systems. This talk explores the potential of trauma memoirs, specifically written by child sexual abuse survivors as a tool for narrative repair and social transformation.

The presentation examines two child sexual abuse trauma memoirs, each authored by an Indian and a Japanese child sexual abuse survivor with comparative lens. Through comparative reading of *It's All in Your Head, m* (2020) by Indian writer, Manjiri Indurkar and *Black Box* (2017) by Japanese reporter, Ito Shiori, this talk focuses on the ways through which these memoirs confront systematic denial, deconstruct cultural taboo, and reclaim agency. For the study, the framework of pluralistic trauma theory is used. The reading acknowledges that trauma is articulated and processed differently from cultural, social, and individual contexts. Both the memoirs reject the culture of silence highly embedded in societies and provide an alternative option to voice their suffering. These memoirs go beyond individual level and talk on collective level while also giving voice to previously marginalized voices of sufferers.

The emerging themes from the memoirs show similarities as well as culturally specific forms of resistance. Indurkar's memoir conveys the ways in which social shame and family denial in an Indian small-town silence the talk about abuse, and her use of dark humour and fragmented narrative structure convey an attempt to restore the self after trauma. Ito's *Black Box* combines her profession, reporting with investigation of personal testimony in order challenge Japanese legal and cultural denial of sexual violence. Her direct storytelling is an act of public activism that insists on having the conversations in a culture where victimhood is met with suspicion. Although the memoirs have differences, they perform narrative innovation by transforming personal memory into social critique. They not only communicate suffering but offer models of resistance and structural change.

These memoirs talk about traumatic memories, resistance, and resilience, breaking cycles of silence and taboo and offering models for collective healing. Thus, these memoirs have potential to nourish more inclusive urban futures. Similar to how circular economies seek to recycle, these memoirs illustrate how traumatic history can be converted into a tool for change, especially in urban communities where silence about abuse continues to prevail.

By taking survivor accounts as part of the cultural infrastructure needed for genuinely inclusive urban regeneration, this lecture argues that literary voices must be made part of the dialogue around innovation. In Indian and Japanese cities, rich in tradition but still struggling with issues of safety, justice, and care in the modern age, literature can be vital in reshaping the emotional and ethical norms of urban lives.

Biogenic synthesis of iron-based compounds by *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* for sustainable removal of selenate from wastewater

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Iron compounds play a crucial role in environmental remediation due to their high surface reactivity and strong affinity toward a wide range of contaminants, including toxic heavy metals and oxyanions. However, their conventional synthesis often requires high temperatures, strong chemical oxidants, or energy-intensive processes that not only increase operational costs but can also generate secondary waste. To develop a more sustainable alternative, this study explores a biologically driven method for synthesizing reactive iron-based compounds using *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*, an iron-oxidizing bacterium known for its ability to convert ferrous to ferric iron.

In this approach, *A. ferrooxidans* was cultivated in iron-rich media, where microbial oxidation facilitated the controlled formation of iron hydroxy sulfate minerals at ambient temperature. The biogenic process produced jarosite as the dominant phase, with distinct morphological variations depending on pH. Compared to non-biogenic jarosite, the biogenic jarosite synthesized under mild conditions (30 °C) demonstrated highest selenate (Se(VI)) removal efficiency. This enhanced performance of biogenic jarosite highlights the crucial role of microbial oxidation in controlling mineral formation to produce well-structured and highly reactive compounds.

To further enhance sustainability and cost efficiency, solid metallic iron and steel plates were introduced as alternative iron sources. These substrates served as the bacterial energy supply and source for mineral formation, enabling a self-sustaining system for producing iron compounds without relying on chemical reagents. On analysis of Se(VI) removal capacity, it was found that iron compound produced from iron/steel plate exhibited potential for removing Se(VI) from aqueous systems. Moreover, the process design allowed the simultaneous synthesis of reactive iron compounds and Se(VI) removal, offering a dual benefit for wastewater treatment.

To improve operational stability, *A. ferrooxidans* was immobilized using a polyurethane sponge matrix, which provided a supportive environment for biofilm development and maintained bacterial activity over extended use. This configuration created a robust and reusable platform suitable for continuous or large-scale applications.

Overall, this research presents a sustainable and eco-friendly route for generating functional iron-based compounds through microbial processes.

OR-5

Soft Magnetic Materials for Sustainable Technologies

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Soft magnetic materials play a pivotal role in enhancing the efficiency and miniaturization of next-generation power electronics. Magnetic cores in inductors and transformers account for nearly half of the total losses in power converters, particularly under high operating frequencies. As power systems evolve toward higher frequencies and compact architectures, the demand for ultra-low-loss soft magnets with high saturation magnetization ($\mu_0 M_s$) and mechanical flexibility has become increasingly critical. Moreover, the scarcity and geopolitical vulnerability of rare-earth elements are accelerating the global transition toward rare-earth-free, high-efficiency motor technologies based on advanced soft magnetic materials, vital for sustainable electrification. To address these challenges, a nanostructure and magnetic domain engineering approach has been developed to fabricate cost-effective, flexible Fe-enriched amorphous ribbons via melt-spinning. Controlled annealing induces partial nanocrystallization of α -Fe within an amorphous matrix and forms a distinctive narrow-stripe domain structure with perpendicular magnetic anisotropy [1]. This transformation from domain wall motion to magnetization rotation reduces core losses by more than 50% compared to the as-quenched state, while maintaining excellent flexibility and high $\mu_0 M_s$ (~ 1.6 T). This strategy provides a versatile pathway toward next-generation, energy-efficient soft magnets tailored for high-frequency operation. Beyond conventional applications, these materials have also been extended to spin-caloritronic functionalities for thermal energy harvesting and heat-flux sensing based on the anomalous Nernst effect. Incorporating high-density nanosized Cu clusters into the amorphous matrix enhances thermopower, yielding a large anomalous Nernst coefficient and power factor [2]. The presentation will highlight the integrated materials design, structure–property correlations, and the broader potential of multifunctional soft magnetic materials in enabling sustainable and energy-resilient technologies.

Acknowledgements

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Multilayer Cryogenic Powder Filters with Low Parasitic Capacitance

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A multilayer cryogenic powder filter has been developed that delivers strong attenuation of radio-frequency (RF) signals in the gigahertz range while minimizing parasitic capacitance to ground. Traditional powder filters, based on a signal wire embedded in a metal powder-filled enclosure, suppress unwanted RF signals via the skin effect but often introduce excess parasitic capacitance between the signal and ground, which can limit the measurement bandwidth in sensitive experiments. By employing a multilayer approach, this new design achieves high RF attenuation and substantially lowers parasitic capacitance. As a result, it efficiently prevents sample heating caused by stray RF signals and preserves the fidelity and bandwidth of precision cryogenic measurements. The combination of robust filtering and minimized capacitive coupling presents a clear advantage for advanced quantum and low-temperature research applications.

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OR-7

Heat Assisted Magnetic Recording (HAMR) and 3D-HAMR as Future Recording Technologies in Hard Disk Drives

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The exponential growth of global data generation, driven by Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial intelligence and cloud computing has created a huge demand for high-capacity data storage solutions [1]. Among the various storage technologies, hard disk drives (HDDs) remain the most cost-effective option for large-scale data storage. For many years, HDDs have used perpendicular magnetic recording (PMR) technology to store data, where the magnetic nanograins on the disk surface are magnetized in an upward or downward direction to represent digital 1s and 0s. The PMR technology uses CoCrPt nanogranular recording media with a magnetocrystalline anisotropy (K_u) of about 0.3 MJ/m³ to store data. However, the grain size cannot be reduced below a certain limit due to its low K_u , making it thermally unstable at the nanoscale and leading to the superparamagnetic effect.

To overcome these limitations, heat-assisted magnetic recording (HAMR) has emerged as the next-generation magnetic recording technology. HAMR utilizes L1₀-ordered FePt grains with a high magnetocrystalline anisotropy of about 6 MJ/m³, ensuring excellent thermal stability even at grain sizes as small as 4 nm. Due to the high K_u value and the corresponding high coercivity, magnetizing these nanograins is not possible using the conventional write head field. Therefore, HAMR employs a nanoscale laser to locally heat the recording medium during the writing process. This temporary heating lowers the magnetic coercivity, allowing data to be written. This enables data to be written at ultra-high densities owing to the smaller grain size and high thermal stability of the grains. Overall, HAMR technology has demonstrated the potential to achieve areal recording densities exceeding 4 Tb/in², far beyond the limits of conventional PMR. Furthermore, HAMR can extend storage capacity through multilevel recording or 3D-HAMR, where data are stored in multiple magnetic states. In this talk, I will present insights and research works on HAMR, 3D-HAMR, and the future directions of this technology.

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Poster Presentations

P1

PD-L1 Blockade Induces Tumor-Specific Lethal Coagulopathy via IL-6–Mediated Thrombin Activation in mice

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Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) targeting the PD-1/PD-L1 axis have revolutionized cancer therapy. However, the phenotypes of their adverse effects remain incompletely understood. In this study, we report a tumor-specific, lethal coagulopathy resembling disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) following administration of an anti-PD-L1 monoclonal antibody (mAb) in the 4T1 breast cancer-bearing mice. Over 50% of Balb/c mice with 4T1 succumbed within one hour of receiving a second anti-PD-L1 dose. This rapid lethality was not observed in mice with other tumor types or those treated with anti-PD-1 mAb.

Pretreatment with antithrombin, anti-IL-6 mAb, or tissue factor pathway inhibitor (TFPI) prevented mortality, indicating a thrombin- and IL-6–dependent mechanism. The lethal phenotype persisted in Rag2^{-/-} mice, suggesting T-cell–independent, innate immune involvement. 4T1-bearing mice suffered splenomegaly, and flow cytometric analysis revealed marked accumulation of CD11b⁺Gr1⁺ myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSCs). Gene expression analysis of MDSC, B cells, CD4 and CD8 T cells revealed that anti-PD-L1 mAb injection elevated IL-6 production in spleen cells. These data indicate that PD-L1 blockade stimulates MDSCs and other innate immune cells to drive IL-6–mediated thrombin activation, culminating in fatal coagulopathy.

Our findings reveal a previously unrecognized, innate immune–driven complication of PD-L1 inhibition, offering mechanistic insight into rare but life-threatening coagulopathies observed in ICI-treated patients.

P2

Defective RNA and Its Helper Virus FbLFV1 Induce Hypovirulence in *Fusarium boothii* : Unveiling a Novel Biocontrol Mechanism

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Viruses are widespread in the kingdom Fungi, with some conferring hypovirulence, although their molecular mechanisms remain largely unclear. (Mizutani et al., 2018) reported three single-stranded RNA viruses co-infecting the *Fusarium boothii* strain Ep-BL13, from Fusarium head blight (FHB)-infested wheat fields in Ethiopia. Among these, a 2,408-nt defective RNA (D-RNA) derived from *Fusarium boothii* large flexivirus 1 (FbLFV1; 12,579 nt) through an internal deletion, confers hypovirulence, characterized by abnormal hyphal growth and reduced sporulation. Molecular and transcriptomic analyses revealed that the D-RNA disrupts the classical secretory pathway, impairing vesicle trafficking, and downregulating transmembrane transporters and plasma membrane-related genes. These findings back up the microscopic evidence of compromised membrane integrity. Together, these results demonstrate that D-RNA-mediated hypovirulence operates by destabilizing plasma membrane structural and functional homeostasis, resembling the action of azole fungicides. This work highlights the potential of sub-viral RNAs as novel biocontrol agents.

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IMMUNE: A Bio-Inspired Framework for Anomaly Detection and Resilience in Cooperative Urban Mobility

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The evolution toward cooperative and connected urban mobility promises efficiency and sustainability but also introduces systemic cyber vulnerabilities capable of triggering cascading disruptions across transportation and energy infrastructures. Traditional centralized security methods suffer from scalability limits and single points of failure, while existing detection models struggle against coordinated attacks in complex urban environments.

We propose IMMUNE (Intelligent Multi-Modal Urban Network Defense) a bio-inspired, decentralized security framework modeled after the adaptive human immune system. Within IMMUNE, every vehicle and infrastructure node acts as an autonomous immune cell, equipped with lightweight danger-signal detectors to identify anomalies in both critical control systems and non-critical data streams. Upon detection, localized “danger” broadcasts trigger a collaborative antibody response, forming a swarm-intelligence-based containment zone that mitigates the spread of cyber threats in real time.

Our framework achieves real-time mitigation of threats without centralized control or prior knowledge of attack signatures. Extensive simulations in a coupled SUMO–OMNeT++ environment demonstrate that IMMUNE achieves sub-second threat containment (500 ms) 58% faster than conventional systems while reducing traffic disruption by 45% and maintaining 95.6% detection accuracy with a 3.2% false positive rate.

By fusing biological resilience principles, swarm, and decentralized AI, IMMUNE offers a transformative pathway toward secure, self-healing, and circularly resilient urban mobility ecosystems.

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P4

Modulating coalescence timing of liquid marbles via wettability adaptation

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Droplet coalescence is a common phenomenon in nature, playing an important role in various industrial and biomedical applications. While uncoated droplets merge upon contact, droplets that are covered with liquid-repellent particles known as “liquid marbles (LMs)” do not coalesce in the same way. Previous work has explored how the particle layer can be triggered to break using external stimuli to control the timing of coalescence. However, programming the timing of droplet coalescence without such stimuli has been difficult. In this study, we present LMs designed to break their particle layers at pre-set times. The particles have a core that is wettable and are connected to a low-wettability flexible molecular chain that gradually increases in wettability over time. This time-dependent change in wettability arises from how the molecular chain adapts, making it a repeatable process whose speed can be managed by adjusting the chain length. As a result, these LMs can reveal their bare droplet surfaces at predetermined times, allowing control over coalescence from 2 to 45 minutes without needing external stimuli. Additionally, the ability to combine the particles allows for precise adjustments of the coalescence timing, achieving resolutions of about one minute. Moreover, the interaction between multiple LMs with varying adaptation times facilitates cascade droplet coalescence, paving the way for new methods of droplet manipulation.

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P5

Diffusion-Controlled Biocorrosion Behaviour of Mg and its Alloys

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Conventional *in vitro* corrosion tests often fail to accurately predict the *in vivo* degradation behaviour of magnesium (Mg) and its alloys. Mg and its alloys have excellent biocompatibility and degradability inside the body, but their high electrochemical reactivity results in rapid hydrogen evolution and ion release under physiological conditions. The diffusion of released ions and gas through surrounding tissues might be a critical factor contributing to discrepancies between *in vitro* and *in vivo* corrosion rates. To address this issue, a model tissue system was developed by introducing an appropriate concentration of a thickener into the cell culture medium [1-3]. The corrosion behaviour of pure Mg and its alloys (WE43 and AZ31) was investigated through immersion tests (up to 28 days) and electrochemical measurements (24 h) at 37 °C under 5% CO₂ in humidified air.

Both immersion and electrochemical studies revealed that the thickener significantly reduced the corrosion rate of Mg and its alloys. Electrochemical tests also indicated suppressing tendency in the corrosion rate by increase in thickner concentrations. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy suggests the high susceptibility of WE43 for change in diffusion rate depends on the drastic change in the electrochemical property of the insoluble salt layer (ISL) formed on the specimen surface. Increase in the thickner concentration significantly reduced the resistance in ISL on WE43 but slightly increased those on pure Mg and AZ31.

The model tissue containing 0.2–0.3% thickener yielded the corrosion rates for pure Mg and AZ31 that closely matched those reported *in vivo* data (subcutaneous implantation in rats), indicating a significant advancement in mimicking intricate clinical and pathological conditions. These results highlight the critical role of diffusion in governing Mg corrosion behaviour and insoluble salt layer formation. The developed model tissue thus offers a promising platform for more physiologically relevant *in vitro* evaluation of biodegradable metallic materials, providing valuable insights into the mechanisms and controlling factors of Mg degradation in biological systems.

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P6

How does Tungsten start deforming?

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【Introduction】

The pop-in phenomenon, marked by abrupt displacement bursts during nanoindentation, offers valuable insights into the initiation of plastic deformation in crystalline materials. While this behavior is relatively well-understood in face-centered cubic (FCC) metals due to their more predictable dislocation dynamics, body-centered cubic (BCC) metals like pure tungsten pose greater challenges. The complex, temperature- and orientation-dependent dislocation behavior in BCC structures makes it difficult to fully characterize the mechanisms governing pop-in events. As tungsten is a key material for high-performance applications in extreme environments, gaining a deeper understanding of its deformation behavior is both scientifically and technologically significant.

【Experimental Methods】

Nanoindentation in the temperature range from room temperature up to 700 °C is performed on pure tungsten. The load at which the event is initiated corresponds to a maximum shear stress beneath the indenter at the very moment of pop-in. Its temperature dependence is analyzed, and activation parameters are deduced to characterize atomistic mechanisms for incipient plasticity. Experimental micromechanical data is accompanied by electron microscopy imaging techniques to analyze the deformation state.

【Results and Conclusion】

According to the shear stresses required for pop-in, the indents can be separated into two populations, one with lower and one with higher required stresses for incipient plasticity to occur. The first population exhibits larger activation volumes and energies than the second. This indicates that different atomistic mechanisms are responsible for the discrepancies between the two populations, meaning that plastic deformation can be initiated with two fundamentally different processes in tungsten. Electron channeling contrast imaging can reveal dislocations in the first 100 nm below the sample surface. The presence or absence of dislocations appears to be decisive for the occurring mechanism in each deformation test.

P7

Developing Novel High-Strength Aluminium Alloys: Synergistic Role of Mg and Li Additions in Al-Si Alloy System

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The quest for weight reduction in automotive and aerospace components continues to drive the development of advanced light alloys with superior mechanical properties. Among these, Al-Si-Mg alloys have gained prominence due to their excellent castability, corrosion resistance, and balanced mechanical behaviour.

In the present work, we focus on the development of novel high-strength aluminium alloys through systematic alloying strategies. First, the effect of Mg addition on the aging and tensile behaviour of squeeze-cast Al-7Si-(x)Mg alloys ($x = 0-0.8$ wt.%) was studied. A significant increase in peak hardness (up to 149 HV) and tensile strength (up to 337 MPa) was observed with increasing Mg content, attributed to precipitation of Mg₂Si phases that effectively impede dislocation motion. Kinetic studies revealed that Mg additions delay aging due to the optimized size and density of precipitates required for maximum strengthening. Strengthening models confirmed that precipitation hardening dominates the yield strength contribution, followed by solid solution strengthening. Microstructural characterization further identified both β'' and β precipitates, indicating a synergistic role in enhancing strength.

Building on these results, Li was introduced into the base Al-7Si-0.8Mg alloy to reduce density while further improving mechanical properties. Li additions led to higher age-hardening response under similar conditions which could be attributed to the combined precipitation of Al₃Li and Mg₂Si phases. The addition of Li not only contributes to additional strengthening but also reduces the alloy density, thereby improving specific strength — a key requirement for aerospace and automotive applications.

The present work highlights a novel alloy design approach by coupling Mg and Li additions to Al-Si systems, enabling the development of lightweight, high-strength alloys with promising potential for structural applications in demanding service environments.

Evaluation of Deterioration Progress Based on Visual Inspection Data of Infrastructures in Fujieda City

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In local cities with limited budgets and personnel, it is important to simplify inspection work based on simple inspection manuals for social infrastructure structures that protect the lives of citizens. On the other hand, Japan mandates a close visual inspection once every five years, and a method for analyzing the inspection results is desirable.

In this study, the proximity visual inspection data was focused on from Fujieda City, Shizuoka Prefecture, a regional city in Japan, and conducted an analysis. Specifically, bridges were grouped by the number of years they had been constructed, separated by 10 years, and the rate of deterioration progression (transition rate) of the bridges was calculated using a Markov chain model. As a result, the differences in the deterioration rate were evaluated by the constructed year, the service periods, the bridge length, the structural type, and the width, etc.

Investigations of Sacrificial Anode Materials and Charging Conditions in the Electrodeposition Method of Reinforced Concrete

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In recent years, as infrastructure continues to age, there is a strong demand for the proper maintenance and management of concrete structures. Various repair methods have been employed up to the present, but problems include low repair efficiency and the risk of corrosion recurring due to corrosive agents remaining inside. In recent years, the electrodeposition method has been attracting attention. To explain the principle of the electro-deposition method, electric current is passed between the reinforcing steel inside the reinforced concrete as the negative electrode and the positive electrode placed on the outside, causing cations in the solution to move electrochemically to the surface of the concrete. These cations form compounds and precipitate on/in the concrete, thereby repairing the concrete. At the same time, corrosion factors such as chloride ions are electrically removed. As a feature, it is highly reliable for repairing concrete based on electrochemical principles; the deposited material preferentially forms on weaker areas such as cracks through electrolysis; and it can remove corrosive substances such as chloride ions. Therefore, the objective of the present study was set to explore the potential of effective anode materials that can replace precious metal electrodes, such as titanium or stainless-steel electrodes.

Based on the findings of the present study, it was demonstrated that sufficient restoration performance can be achieved by employing zinc or aluminum as sacrificial anodes, thereby providing viable and cost-effective alternatives to conventionally utilized, high-cost electrodes such as titanium. Furthermore, during the repair process, the application of magnesium acetate as the external electrolyte solution, in conjunction with a current density of 1.0 A/m², resulted in the most effective coverage of surface cracks and the surrounding concrete matrix.

Study on the Incorporation Methods of Bacteria and Organic Matters in Self-Healing Concrete

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Concrete structures are inevitably subjected to harsh environmental conditions, resulting in crack formation that accelerates reinforcement corrosion and shortens service life. In recent years, self-healing concrete incorporating microorganisms has gained attention due to its ability to autonomously seal cracks through microbial precipitation of calcium carbonate.

This study explores practical methods for incorporating microorganisms into concrete, focusing on their preservation, activation, and healing performance. Microorganisms were treated via freeze-drying (lyophilization) to ensure stability and ease of handling prior to mixing. Their ability to regain biological activity and contribute to crack healing upon rehydration was evaluated. Additionally, drying at 60 °C was examined as an alternative method, using both frozen and liquid microbial states.

The investigation was conducted from four key perspectives:

1. Comparison of freeze-drying and thermal drying (60 °C) as microbial powdering techniques.
2. Incorporation of treated microorganisms into mortar and assessment of crack closure and calcium carbonate formation.
3. Evaluation of yeast extract and PHBV as nutrient sources and scaffolding materials to enhance microbial activity.
4. Observation of healing performance under varying crack widths and nutrient conditions.

Both freeze-dried microorganisms and those thermally dried from the liquid state demonstrated calcium carbonate precipitation at crack sites, confirming their potential for self-healing functionality. Additionally, currently, demonstration experiments using actual concrete structures are underway at research facilities in Ehime and Kanagawa, aiming to validate the field applicability of this approach.

Non-destructive Investigations on Urethane Elastomer Coatings Exposed to Marine Environment for 15 Years

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Corrosion protection using coating materials is a key countermeasure for offshore steel structures against corrosion. These coatings are primarily applied to steel located above -1.0m from low water level (L.W.L. -1.0m) to protect the steel from corrosion by blocking water, oxygen, chloride ions, and other corrosion-related factors. Various types of coating methods have been established for coating corrosion protection, including painting, organic coating, petrolatum coating, metal coating, and inorganic coating. In the maintenance of port and harbor facilities with coatings for corrosion protection, it is necessary to predict the decline in performance of the coatings at the time of maintenance planning, and to set an appropriate time to take countermeasures. However, the actual condition of the performance of the coating material and its corrosion protection effect after long-term use is not clear for any type of coating corrosion protection including organic coating. At present, a prediction method for deterioration has not been established. In this study, the aging changes in the performance of various types of coating protection on test pieces and actual structures were investigated based on non-destructive tests in order to establish a method for predicting the degradation of various types of coating protection. Furthermore, in the context of investigating efficient non-destructive testing methods, the practicality of three-dimensional shape measurement was also assessed. As a result, it was confirmed that the performance of the coating material retained sufficient corrosion protection effect, although a decrease in volume resistivity was observed in some parts. In addition, it was confirmed that the thickness of the steel from above the coating was accurately evaluated by both the very-low-frequency eddy-current testing and electromagnetic ultrasonic methods. The three-dimensional shape measurement confirmed that surface undulations were captured with high accuracy.

P12 Single-electron tunneling in silicon-on-insulator highly-doped nanoscale transistors

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In recent decades, low-power electronics becomes essential to sustain the exponential growth of computing necessities, reduce environmental impact, and enable other advanced technologies. Single-electron tunneling (SET) provides a pathway to operate electronic devices with low energy (one electron at a time), but compatibility with CMOS technology is also important [1].

For that purpose, we study nanoscale silicon-on-insulator (SOI) transistors fabricated in our Cleanroom, doped with impurities of both types (donors and acceptors) at high concentrations (one or two orders of magnitude higher than the metal-insulator transition (MIT) concentration) [2]. In such a regime of concentration, it is expected that the SOI transistors exhibit metallic properties [3,4], i.e., control of the channel potential by a gate voltage is expected to be difficult. However, we will show that codoping and nano-patterning [4] of the channel can allow the formation of quantum dots (QDs) and the observation of SET behavior based on the Coulomb blockade effect.

Since such QDs are likely formed by dopants (most likely by clusters of donors) [5], the barrier height is not very large and may be comparable with the thermal energy at room temperature (a few tens of meV) [6]. Therefore, we study the properties of such devices at low temperatures, usually at $T \approx 8$ K, to effectively suppress thermal activation of carriers and observe SET transport [7]. This approach is also aligned with the recent trend for development of cryo-electronics.

In this work, we show that SOI transistors codoped with comparable doping concentrations can exhibit SET behavior in several cases. The devices have doping concentrations of phosphorus (P) donor, N_D , and boron (B) acceptors, N_A , on the order of $5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, about one order higher than the MIT. The thickness of the SOI layer is about 15 nm, and the lateral dimensions (width and length) are on the order of 20-50 nm. Several devices in which the gate leakage current is not significant exhibit the clear signatures of SET behavior, which are current peaks in the I_D - V_G characteristics and Coulomb diamonds in the stability diagrams (plots of $\text{abs}(I_D)$ in the V_G - V_D space).

In conclusion, the results demonstrated that the conditions suitable for SET low-power operation can be obtained by combining nano-dimensionality, codoping and low-temperature.

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P13

Design and development of segmented $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb, Bi})_2$ -based thermoelectric devices

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$\text{Mg}_3\text{Sb}_2\text{-Mg}_3\text{Bi}_2$ solid solutions are potential candidates for low-to-medium temperature thermoelectric power generation. Previous studies suggest doped n-type Sb-rich $\text{Mg}_3\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}$ compositions are superior in the medium temperature (600-800 K), whereas Bi-rich $\text{Mg}_3\text{Bi}_{1.5}\text{Sb}_{0.5}$ compositions show their peak performance below 550 K. Segmenting Sb-rich and Bi-rich $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb, Bi})_2$ compounds is a potential method to improve the conversion efficiency of $\text{Mg}_3\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}$ TE devices.

In this study, we developed a two-step fabrication technique to segment $\text{Mg}_3\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}$ and $\text{Mg}_3\text{Bi}_{1.5}\text{Sb}_{0.5}$ using a thin metal foil contact layer. Low contact resistivities ($< 10 \mu\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$) were observed at the $\text{Mg}_3\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}/\text{Mg}_3\text{Bi}_{1.5}\text{Sb}_{0.5}$ junctions. The segment-height-ratio optimization was carried-out using finite element method to maximize the efficiency gain from segmentation. The efficiency evaluation of single and multi-segment $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb, Bi})_2$ TE legs confirm the effectiveness of segmentation in improving the TE conversion efficiency. The construction, one-step segmentation process optimization, and performance evaluation of $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb, Bi})_2$ segmented devices will be discussed in detail.

Investigation of Performance of n-type Mg_3Sb_2 at High Temperatures for Thermoelectric Device Fabrication

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The n-type Mg_3Sb_2 has a great potential for waste heat recovery due to its superior thermoelectric (TE) properties¹. It has also advantages like low density, absence of toxic elements and low TE module fabrication cost. To accelerate the commercialisation of this material, the Mg evaporation/migration at high temperatures, which the material may be subjected to during the module fabrication stages, has to be addressed. There have been some techniques followed like applying a surface coating, Mg vapour annealing² etc. so that the effect of Mg migration is minimised at high temperatures. But a simpler and more inexpensive approach involves adding excess Mg to the parent composition or increasing the Mg content in the initial stoichiometry. In the present study, a simple, cost-effective method of increasing Mg content in initial stoichiometry, is followed. The synthesised compositions are subjected to high temperature conditions under different atmospheric conditions, and their TE performance are evaluated. It is observed that heating in partial pressure conditions under high vacuum maintains TE properties better after heating compared to heating the samples in static low vacuum conditions. Their thermoelectric properties are determined and compared so that an optimum excess Mg amount to be added to the parent composition could be estimated. Further, the joining process at suitable high temperatures are carried out the performance is investigated.

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P15

Scientific Analysis of Pigments Used in Hand-Colored Photographs from Brinkley's *Japan*

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Hand-coloured photographs are monochrome photographs to which colour was added by hand. In Japan, they gained immense popularity, particularly the Yokohama photographs sold as souvenirs for foreigners visiting Japan during the late Edo and Meiji periods. They were produced in large quantities and exported overseas. Hand-colouring was mainly applied to albumen prints by painters trained in ukiyo-e and colour woodblock practices. Previous studies have indicated that, alongside traditional Japanese pigments and dyes, newly introduced synthetic organic colourants were also employed. Furthermore, it has been suggested that colouring techniques from ukiyo-e woodblock printing were adapted for this purpose.

This study aims to scientifically analyze the hand-coloured photograph “*Theatrical performance*” included in Volume 10 of *Japan: Described and Illustrated by the Japanese*, edited by Francis Brinkley, and to elucidate the pigments, binding media (coatings), and techniques used in Japanese hand-coloured photographs of the late 19th to early 20th centuries. To examine the pigments and colouring procedure used on this print, a set of non-destructive analytical techniques was applied. Infrared and ultraviolet photography were first conducted to investigate the infrared transmission/absorption properties of the colourants and to detect fluorescence under UV excitation. Optical microscopy and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) were then used to examine surface features and determine the elemental composition. In addition, spectral reflectance measurements, 3D fluorescence (EEM) spectrum, and FT-IR were employed to further characterise organic colouring materials and the binding/coating layers.

The analyses revealed that the red areas were coloured with vermilion, blue with prussian blue, and the green and yellow-green hues were achieved by mixing orpiment with prussian blue and related pigments. These results provide insights into the materials and colouring techniques used in Japanese hand-coloured photographs produced during this period.

Figure 1. “*Theatrical performance*” of Japan:
Described and Illustrated by the Japanese
(Collection of the Laboratory)

Projected Intensification of Extreme Winds over Japan

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Extreme winds pose significant risks to infrastructure, energy systems, and socioeconomic activities in various regions over Japan, where typhoons are a major driver of damaging winds. Understanding how these extremes may change under future climate conditions is essential for improving resilience and disaster preparedness. This study investigates projected changes in extreme winds across major Japanese cities derived from a dataset of large-ensemble climate simulations, called d4PDF, for the historical climate and future climate scenarios with +2K, and +4K warming. We find that extreme wind speeds increased under warmer climate conditions, with the largest rises in southern cities such as Fukuoka, Kochi, and Kagoshima. The percentage change in +4 K simulations (up to 13%) is nearly twice that of +2 K (up to 8%), which indicates stronger intensification of rare and high-impact wind events in future climate.

Analysis of tropical cyclone (TC) influences reveals that TC days associated with extreme winds remain similar or slightly increase under warmer climates. Southern cities exhibit the strongest TC influence, suggesting that typhoons will continue to play a dominant role in bringing extreme winds. Our overall study highlights that future intensification of extreme winds in Japan will likely remain primarily driven by tropical cyclones, and suggests the need for continued typhoon-resilience planning.

P17 (IL-13)

Impact of seagrass meadows and macroalgae beds on the concentration of carbon and nutrients in shallow coastal areas

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The restoration of seagrass meadows and macroalgae beds in shallow coastal areas is an attractive research topic not only because of its environmental importance, but also because of the ecological and socioeconomic services it provides. Seagrass meadows and macroalgae beds have proven effective for carbon sequestration and for maintaining shallow coastal waters (control of acidity, aeration, etc.). On the other hand, submerged vegetation in coastal areas usually supports rich ecosystems and serves as habitat for lower trophic levels (benthic animals, bivalves, epiphytic algae, etc.) that are essential for maintaining higher trophic levels (demersal and pelagic fishes) in the global coastal ecosystem.

To study how different types of vegetation affect dissolved organic matter distribution and major nutrient concentrations, our group has developed a high-resolution numerical model that accounts for submerged vegetation and the benthic ecosystems associated with it. In this opportunity, we would like to present our results for four cases in Kanazawa Bay, a small bay located south of Yokohama that is representative of typical Japanese coastal areas. We proposed three study scenarios: 1) actual vegetation, 2) no seagrass meadows, 4) only macroalgae farming activities. In these scenarios, we followed the ratio between dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) and dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP) (DIN/DIP), the dissolved organic carbon (DOC) concentration, and the dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) concentration during 12 months.

Our results summarize the seasonal behavior of the studied species in shallow coastal areas, while providing insightful information on the importance of coastal vegetation in controlling nutrients and carbon concentration in water. Because of the importance of a better understanding and the assessment of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) present and future projects, we consider that simulations could be an important tool to maintain balance between environmental solutions and the ecological services of a target study area.

P18

Temporal variations in phytoplankton community structure and environmental conditions in Suruga Bay during 2024

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Phytoplankton community structure is important for marine ecosystems. In this study, we investigated seasonal variations in the taxonomical composition of phytoplankton community in the offshore Suruga Bay during 2024, based on the high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis of photosynthetic pigments (chlorophylls and carotenoids).

Field surveys were conducted onboard the R/V Hokuto monthly during 2024 at two stations in Suruga Bay, st. SR1 and st. SR3 located in the inner and central areas of the bay, respectively. Seawater samples for photosynthetic pigment analysis were collected from six layers between 0 m and 75 m depths using Niskin bottles attached to the automated sampling system (SBE55 ECO) and a bucket. Simultaneously, the vertical distributions of water temperature and salinity was measured using a CTD sensor. The quantitative analysis of each photosynthetic pigment in the phytoplankton community was performed using a HPLC system with a C8 column (Zapata et al. 2000). Based on the pigment composition data, the biomass of each taxonomic group was estimated as Chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) concentration using CHEMTAX software, a matrix factorization program (Mackey et al. 1996; 1997).

At both the two stations, vertical mixing of water-column was observed in January–February, while stratification of water-column was well developed in August–September. At the inner area station (st. SR1), prasinophytes and cryptophytes accounted for a large proportion of the total community biomass in January–March, diatoms dominated in June and November–December, and cyanobacteria dominated in August. *Prochlorococcus* was detected year-round, except for March–April. Cyanobacteria biomass was high at 75 m in January and at the surface layer in June–September. At the central area station (st. SR3), the total community biomass was high at 0–50 m in December–April. In March, the total community biomass was particularly high at 10–20 m, where cryptophytes and dinoflagellates dominated.

P19

Structural Dynamics of Thailand's Tuna Imports and Exports

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Objective: Thailand is a significant global tuna processing hub, accounting for 26 % of the global export value of canned tuna in 2023. However, Thailand does not have tuna fishing fleets and heavily relies on imported raw materials. In this study, we analyze the time-series evolution of Thailand's frozen tuna imports and canned tuna exports from 1996 to 2024, with the aim of examining the underlying factors driving the structural changes in both import and export patterns.

Methods: Our analysis is based on official tuna import and export data compiled by the Department of Fisheries, Thailand, covering the period from 1996 to 2024. This timeframe was selected as 1996 marks the first year for which consistent and detailed data were available from this source. Tuna products are classified according to their corresponding Harmonized System (HS) codes (0303.43 and 1604.14, etc.).

Results: Tunas are mainly imported frozen and consistently account for over 90% of annual tuna imports over the study period. Skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) is the primary raw material for canned tuna, representing more than 70 % of frozen tuna imports each year. The import of frozen tuna from the long-term major suppliers, such as Taiwan, Japan, and the USA, has declined, while Pacific Island Countries (PICs) have expanded rapidly, surpassing the share of the former group for the first time in 2022. Meanwhile, the export destinations of canned tuna have diversified, shifting from mature Western markets in North America and Europe toward growing markets, especially in Western Asia and Africa. Furthermore, this study explores the underlying factors driving the shifts, including regulatory reforms and governance issues. The transformation demonstrates the flexibility and adaptability of Thailand's canned tuna industry to various constraints. These resiliencies are a key factor for Thailand to sustain its competitiveness as the world's leading producer and exporter of canned tuna.

Scientific Analysis of Painting Materials in the Greek Icon “The Baptism of Christ”

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Icons are sacred paintings, primarily executed in tempera on wooden panels, venerated in the Eastern Orthodox Church. They have long been used in liturgical contexts as well as displayed in private homes. As Orthodox Christianity spread, icon production continued in various regions, adhering to traditional conventions, yet exhibiting distinct regional and stylistic differences. This study aims to systematically conduct scientific analyses of icon paintings preserved in Japan in order to clarify the materials and techniques used in their creation. In the history of icon conservation, it is known that restorative interventions involving overpainting of deteriorated areas rather than the current approach of minimal intervention were commonly performed. Through scientific investigation, this study also seeks to explore the conservation and restoration history of icons and their practices. This presentation focuses on the Greek icon “The Baptism of Christ” (18th century, Tamagawa University Museum of Education) and reports the results of raking light, infrared, and ultraviolet photography, as well as optical microscopy and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analyses.

The analytical results indicate the presence of calcium sulfate in the ground layer; red and brown areas containing iron oxide; blue areas colored with Prussian blue (Fig. 1); and green areas created by yellow orpiment and Prussian blue (Fig. 2). Areas exhibiting different responses under infrared and ultraviolet illumination showed the presence of titanium and chromium in XRF analysis, suggesting later retouching during modern restoration.

Figure 1 XRF spectrum of blue No.1 area Figure 2 XRF spectrum of green No.1 area

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Low-Cost Si-Based Platforms for High-Efficiency Solar Cells in Mobility Applications

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The growing demand for solar-powered electric vehicles drives the need for high-efficiency and low-cost photovoltaic technologies. III–V multi-junction solar cells offer outstanding performance but are limited by the high cost of Ge and GaAs substrates. Replacing these with Si provides a scalable and economically viable alternative; however, lattice and thermal mismatches between Si and III–V materials hinder direct heteroepitaxial growth.^[1] Introducing a compositionally graded SiGe buffer layer effectively alleviates these mismatches by providing a gradual transition in lattice constant. Nevertheless, conventional fabrication of such buffer layers typically requires epitaxial growth techniques, high-vacuum systems, and elevated processing temperatures, which significantly increase manufacturing cost and complexity. Developing a simplified, low-temperature approach for SiGe buffer formation is therefore essential for realizing large-area, low-cost Si-based platforms suitable for next-generation mobility applications.

This study demonstrates a simple, low-cost method to form SiGe buffer layers on Si using various screen-printed aluminum–germanium (Al–Ge) pastes of different ratios (4:6–7:3) followed by thermal annealing at 800 °C.^[2] The process induces localized liquid-phase epitaxy (LPE)-like behavior without vacuum equipment, suitable for large-area fabrication.

Cross-sectional SEM imaging (Fig. 1a) reveals a continuous SiGe layer formed at the Si interface, confirming uniform reaction across the substrate. EDX depth profiling (Fig. 1b) shows that increasing the Al content from 4:6 to 7:3 produces thicker but more Si-rich layers, while the 5:5 and 5.5:4.5 compositions yield the highest surface Ge concentration (~85 at.%). Raman spectra (Fig. 1c) exhibit systematic peak shifts corresponding to strain relaxation and compositional variation within the SiGe layer. Photoluminescence measurements (Fig. 1d) show a clear red-shift and enhanced intensity for the 5:5 sample, indicating Ge incorporation, bandgap narrowing, and improved crystalline quality. Overall, the results demonstrate effective control of layer structure and optical response through Al–Ge composition tuning.

This work establishes a scalable, cost-effective route to fabricate graded SiGe buffer layers on Si by tuning Al–Ge composition and annealing. The approach enables precise control of structural and optical properties, advancing III–V solar cell integration on low-cost Si substrates for lightweight mobility applications.

Figure 1. (a) Cross-sectional SEM image of SiGe layer at the Si interface. (b) EDX depth profiles for various Al–Ge ratios. (c) Raman and (d) PL spectra showing strain relaxation and red-shifted emission with Ge

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Design and Optimization of FePt-Based Multilevel HAMR Media for High-Capacity and Energy-Efficient Data Storage

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The demand for reliable, low-cost digital storage drives the need to increase HDD areal density. Multi-level heat-assisted magnetic recording (HAMR) can push capacities toward 10 Tbit in⁻², and the FePt/Ru/FePt tri-layer was the first demonstrated 3D-HAMR [1]. However, Ru has a low lattice misfit with L1₀-FePt which caused in-plane variants, poor L1₀ ordering in the initial 1 nm of the top FePt layer, and grain disordering [2]. Since larger lattice misfit and epitaxial strain suppress variants and enforce a [001] texture, we explored molybdenum (Mo) as an alternative spacer. Mo has a 15.3 % misfit to L1₀-FePt and limited solubility, which should flatten the FePt/Mo interface and improve top-layer growth. Tri-layer film FePt-40C (3.5nm)/ Mo-40C (2nm)/ FePt-40C (3.5nm) were sputtered on MgO (001) at 600 °C, then characterized by XRD, SQUID, TEM, and EDS. TEM show a well-separated granular microstructure (average grain size ≈ 8.6 nm) with a flat FePt/Mo interface. Magnetic measurements reveal strong perpendicular anisotropy and distinct coercivities for the top (≈ 0.92 T) and bottom (≈ 3.04 T) FePt layers. There is a slight kink around 0.2T which corresponds to the decoupling between top and bottom magnetic layers. Both magnetic layers exhibit L1₀ ordering, though EDS detects a slight Mo diffusion into the top FePt, which can degrade ordering. To mitigate this, we propose (i) optimizing layer thicknesses and deposition conditions and (ii) using h-BN as a segregant for industrial implementation. This work elucidates how a flat FePt/Mo interface and Mo-spacer optimization enhance multi-level HAMR performance.

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Synergistic Enhancement of Dielectric Properties in High-Entropic Perovskite Oxides-Based Polymeric Nanocomposites for Energy Harvesting and Sensing

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In response to the growing ecological challenges associated with conventional energy-harvesting technologies, flexible and environmentally responsible PVDF-based piezoelectric nanogenerators (PENGs) were developed by incorporating high-entropy perovskite oxide nanoparticles ($\text{Bi}_{0.2}\text{Na}_{0.2}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{Ba}_{0.2}\text{TiO}_3$ (BNSCB) as functional fillers. Systematic evaluation of the structural, thermal, and electrical properties revealed that the 7 wt% BNSCB-loaded PVDF (PBB-7) nanocomposite exhibits markedly enhanced performance. The incorporation of BNSCB nanoparticles significantly promotes electroactive β -phase nucleation, achieving a high polar phase fraction of $F(\beta) > 85\%$ compared to pristine PVDF. Piezo-response force microscopy further confirms an enhanced piezoelectric coefficient ($d_{33} \approx 34$ pm/V), corresponding to a notable pressure sensitivity of 1.642 V/kPa in the medium pressure range. Under a 10 N mechanical load, the optimized PENG delivers a high output of 35 V, 4.7 μA , and 65 μW with remarkable durability exceeding 15,000 cycles, making it well-suited for practical applications such as powering LEDs, charging capacitors, and monitoring biomechanical movements. The device efficiently charges capacitors, powers light-emitting diodes, and enables real-time motion detection, also functioning as a self-powered pressure sensor. These results demonstrate the strong potential of PVDF@BNSCB nanocomposites for circular economy-driven applications, including ambient energy harvesting, wearable sensors, motion monitoring, and next-generation self-powered microelectronic systems.

Transition Metal Halide Perovskite Derivatives for High-Performance All-Solid-State Batteries: Breaking the Conductivity Barrier

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Abstract:

Transition metals are highly effective catalysts, and their incorporation into halide perovskite derivatives offers a strategic route to tune structural and electronic properties for enhanced catalytic and electrochemical performance¹⁻⁴. Hybrid organic-inorganic perovskite derivatives remain a promising yet underexplored class of cathodes for all-solid-state lithium batteries (ASSLBs)⁵⁻⁷. Understanding the *d*-orbital occupancy and spin states of these metals during redox processes is critical for realizing the full battery potential. Here, we report (DMAP)₂CuCl₄, a copper-based perovskite derivative with 4-(dimethylamino)pyridinium cations, as a high-capacity cathode. It crystallizes in the monoclinic *C2/c* space group, is thermally stable up to 200 °C, and has an optical bandgap of 2.45 eV. EPR confirms redox-active Cu²⁺/Cu⁺ centers. All solid-state battery (ASSBs) using argyrodite Li₆PS₅Cl found to suppress cathode dissolution observed in liquid electrolytes with a capacity of 180 mAh/g at 298 K, which further increases to 550 mAh/g at 334 K. Ex-situ XRD and TOF-SIMS reveal synergistic capacity contributions from multi-electron Cu reduction, Cl⁻/Li⁺ exchange, and organic cation lithiation, establishing design principles for temperature-optimized, stable hybrid cathodes. These findings proposed a design principle for stabilizing hybrid organic-inorganic cathodes in solid-state batteries through protective interfacial coatings and temperature-optimized operation strategies.

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